

MERGE

MEASURING WHAT MATTERS

Policy pathways toward inclusive and sustainable wellbeing

Deliverable D1.2

Beyond GDP policy repository

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1. Description of the task

This deliverable is part of MERGE Task 1.3 'Metasynthesis of beyond GDP policies for a policy repository'. The objective of this task was to collect real-life examples of policies, from around the world, that contribute to sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (SIW)¹ and to make them easily available for policymakers and other relevant stakeholders. This task was carried out in three stages or sub-tasks: i) Identifying and prioritising policies that are particularly relevant for advancing SIW; ii) collecting evidence from existing examples of the implementation of those policies and writing case descriptions of each example (referred to as 'case studies' in the context of this task); and iii) uploading these case studies into the ZOE-owned Sustainable Prosperity policy database for their easy online access (available at <https://sustainable-prosperity.eu/policy-database/>, last accessed 28/01/2026). In parallel, because this list combines policies originating from projects and sources utilising various beyond GDP frameworks and approaches (such as degrowth, a-growth, or post-development), we created a summary table clarifying for general audiences the key characteristic and differences between those approaches, notably with regards to the three dimensions of SIW: wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability.

The Sustainable Prosperity website and its policy database pre-date the MERGE project. At the time of the start of the task, this database included a list of around 280 policy entries, with a short high-level definition of the policy for each entry, often on a theoretical or abstract level, with no concrete examples of their concrete application. Thus, the first sub-task involved reviewing this policy repository, as well as other promising policies identified by MERGE sister projects (more specifically, SPES, ToBe, REAL, and WISE Horizons), to create the list of key innovative policies most susceptible to advance sustainable and inclusive wellbeing that would be covered in subsequent steps. In a second step, to support policymakers on why and how to implement these policies, we conducted desk-based research to find concrete examples of the real-life implementation of each of the selected policies, and especially information about the impact and lessons learned from those experiences. Based on this information, we developed short descriptions of these examples, called 'case studies' in the database, in a format that can be easily communicated to

¹ In this task, we adopt the concept of Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW), a framework that has become a new common ground in the Beyond GDP field for advancing the overarching policy goal of wellbeing of all people of current and future generations, and of the planet.. The convergence towards this concept has been further analysed and explained in MERGE Deliverable D1.3. 'A synthesis of models, metrics, and policies for a sustainable and inclusive wellbeing future'.

policymakers and other stakeholders. Lastly, these case studies were uploaded to the policy database on the Sustainable Prosperity website, either complementing existing policy entries that did not have information on real-world examples, or introducing new policy instruments to the database. The Sustainable Prosperity policy database was thus used as an input in the first part of the task (in which we selected the most relevant policies), as well as an output of this task insofar as additional content was added to it. All added content has been properly referenced and linked to the MERGE project.

These three sub-tasks are further explained in the following sections.

2. Identification and prioritisation of policies

At the time of starting the Task, the Sustainable Prosperity policy database consisted of a list of around 280 policy entries that covered different policy areas, sectors, and governance levels, among others. With the goal of identifying the most relevant policies and promising practices for our future work in the MERGE project, we decided to take this sample as a starting point and then narrow down the scope. To do so, we began by conducting a broad scanning of all policy entries available in the database. Based on this initial scan, and because many of those entries were very specific, we gathered policy instruments that relate to each other into clusters. We then assigned a ‘higher-level’ policy name to each cluster, which captured the essence of the grouped policy instruments (see example in Table 1).

Table 1: Example of clustering

Policy name	Related entries in SP database
Encourage employee ownership and social enterprises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax relief and financial support instruments for cooperative platform companies • Tax benefits for employee cooperatives • Reduction of bureaucratic barriers and accounting requirements for cooperatives • Creation of a separate legal form for democratic / participative companies

In some cases, we found that some existing policy entries already represented a ‘higher-level’ policy by themselves, so these clusters contained only a single policy entry. For example, this was the case for ‘Universal Basic Income’.

Following these exercises of clustering, and assigning a policy name, the first prioritisation of the policies was guided by the following criteria:

- The policy works towards at least two of the following goals: wellbeing (wellbeing today), inclusion (wellbeing for all), and sustainability (wellbeing in the future).
- The chosen policies are a mix of both (supra)national level policies as well as regional/ local level policies.
- The policy has high transformative potential for systems change (rather than being reactive).

Based on the scanning and clustering mentioned above, we have initially created a list of 29 policies.

In addition to the clusters and policies derived from the existing database entries, in this Task, we have added six new policy entries to the database (see 'new additions' in list below). The new policies aim to complement the existing entries by offering new policy ideas that work ambitiously towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing. Their selection was based on past work done by the consortium partners, and aligned with the policy selection criteria as outlined above.

For each policy that was defined, we looked for 1) examples of a real-life implementation of the policy and; 2) evidence on the impact that this policy has had. The goal of exploring case studies for each policy was to learn whether these have been implemented in real life, and if there are case studies available that investigate their key design features and effects. To explore their implementation and evaluation in more depth, we carried out a second prioritisation process, following a pragmatic approach based on the evidence available and consortium partners' knowledge, to focus on those where implementation is most promising and documented. The final list consisted of 15 policies:

- Basic income
- Free or low-fare public transport (**new addition**)
- Universal Job guarantee
- High inheritance tax
- Community wealth building (**new addition**)
- Cap on income or maximum pay differentials
- Encourage local food production (**new addition**)
- Common trusts
- Encourage decentralised and distributed energy

- Universal Basic Services **(new addition)**
- Encouraging regenerative and distributive businesses **(new addition)**
- Granting rights to nature **(new addition)**
- Support sustainable social innovations
- Wellbeing budgets
- Working time reduction

3. Development of the case studies

For each of these 15 policies, we carried out desk research to identify where they have been implemented in practice. To gather input on the impact of each policy, we searched for existing evidence using the key words “case study”, “evaluation”, “impact”, “meta-analysis”, “systematic review”, “[policy name]”. When available, we also looked at the official website of the policy initiative.

One-hour interviews were held with representatives of each of the MERGE sister projects - ToBe, SPES, REAL, with the exception of WISE Horizons, of which one of the authors (Nicole Kormann da Silva) was a member of this task group – to ensure that the case studies were informed by the latest insights and reports from these projects.

The information gathered was compiled into a short summary for each case study, organised as follows: 1) case description, which outlines the policy and its objectives, 2) policy impact and evaluation, which summarises the publicly available evidence on the policy’s impacts and results, and 3) references. To read the complete description and case studies of the 15 policies covered in this task, please see the Annex. As mentioned above, these summaries have been added to the database on the Sustainable Prosperity website (see section 4).

4. Use of and publication on the Sustainable Prosperity website

4.1. Rationale

The Sustainable Prosperity website was originally created by ZOE Institute as part of a project financed by the KR Foundation, Robert Bosch Stiftung and Partners for a New Economy. This website seeks to present policymakers and other relevant stakeholders with arguments for the necessity of going beyond current growth-centric policymaking to achieve sustainable prosperity. It also showcases how the policy design process should be carried out and what policies could enable this transformation. On the last point, previous work involved identifying from the academic literature innovative policy approaches to move Europe into the "safe and just space for humanity" and organising them into a coherent structure. Considering the strong methodology used for compiling this list of priorities, reviewing over 80 sources and based on a policy framework inspired by the United Nations, we considered it a solid database of policy examples that can contribute to sustainable and inclusive wellbeing. As such, it was a suitable point of departure for our work in this task.

In addition, publishing the case studies resulting from this work directly on the Sustainable Prosperity is strategic for several reasons. First, because this website is a living space that allows for the collection and alignment of findings from the various EU-funded research projects into one online platform, maximising the visibility of all of them. Second, because 9 out of 15 policies covered by this task come from the Sustainable Prosperity website, this choice avoids duplication of efforts and rather improves what already exists. Third, because as this website was created before the task, it already had users and will continue to be used beyond the project lifespan, allowing for a more lasting use of MERGE results.

4.2. Data protection and compliance with GDPR

The Sustainable Prosperity website is publicly available and has been developed over many years by ZOE Institute with the support of several funders and partners noted in the About Us section of the website. Content should be used in line with its privacy policy. Personal data (name, e-mail) is not collected unless users subscribe to the newsletter or contact us. The website collects analytics data in line with its privacy policy.

4.3. Integration of MERGE work into the website

The case studies conducted as part of this project were added to the Sustainable Prosperity website in the section 'Policy Tools' and the subsection 'Policy Database' available at the following link: <https://sustainable-prosperity.eu/policy-database/> (see Figure 1)

Figure 1: Menu of the Sustainable Prosperity website

In the policy repository, users can specifically look for the policies with a case study by using the filter section on the left, selecting the option ‘has a case study’ (see Figure 2). The filtering system also structures the database and allows users to look for policies with respect to their expected contribution to political and sustainability objectives, as well as their impact by sectoral and governance level, target group, instrument type and immediacy of effect.

Policy Database

Figure 2: Interface of the Policy Database

Below you can find an example comparing the content and the structure that is available on the Sustainable Prosperity for those policies not covered by the MERGE case studies (see

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Figure 3) with the content that was added as part of MERGE (see Figure 4 and Figure 5). While original entries only contained two to three descriptive sentences, with keywords and a source, thanks to the MERGE project, the 15 policy entries now include a long description and one to four new tabs with the case studies associated with the policy.

Air expansion moratorium

Description

Stop growth of aviation sector by placing a moratorium on any aviation infrastructure or growth in flight paths.

Source

Reckman, E. Sanchez-Blancuez, N. (2019). Moratoria on new airport infrastructure, and scaling down of airports. Stay Grounded.

Keywords

airport,air travel,air transport,transport,mobility

Tags

Regulation

Supranational

National

Transport Policy

Environmental Policy

Medium-term

Mobility and transport

Figure 3: Example of a policy entry 'Air expansion moratorium' not covered under T1.3 of the MERGE project

Universal Basic Services

Description Case Study 1 Case Study 2

The term ‘universal basic services’ refers to the proposal to develop more and better collectively provided services that are free for all who need them, regardless of someone’s income or status. Potential benefits of universal basic services include (Coote, Kasliwal & Percy, 2019):

- Equity: providing public services reduce income inequalities as they meet basic needs on which low-income groups spend much of their income.
- Efficiency: by reducing transaction costs, avoiding duplication, and facilitating coordinated efforts across various services, UBS can deliver more effective and cost-efficient outcomes compared to market-driven approaches.
- Solidarity: USB can promote shared responsibility, create opportunities for diverse social interactions and reduce inequalities.
- Sustainability: UBS can ensure long-term stability by focusing on prevention, helping stabilise economies and promoting environmentally friendly practices.

There is a wide range of innovative policies aimed at enhancing affordability and accessibility of public services around the world. Public services can cover many sectors such as

- Housing: for example, Vienna (Austria) maintains affordable housing through municipal land ownership and subsidies;
- Transport: Luxembourg offers free public transportation across the whole country;
- Healthcare: the UK, France, Sweden (and more) offer universal free or heavily subsidised healthcare;
- Education: Public universities in Iceland, Slovenia, Argentina, Brazil, Finland (and more) are free or charge low tuition fees

This entry was added as part of the MERGE research project (funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, grant agreement N° 101132524).

Source

Coote, A., Kasliwal, P., & Percy, A. (2019). Universal basic services: Theory and practice-a literature review.

Keywords

housing,transport,healthcare,education

Tags

- Regulation
- National
- Transport Policy
- Social Welfare Policy
- Health Policy
- Short-term
- Medium-term
- Food
- Water
- Mobility and transport
- Housing and construction
- Electrical energy and heat

Figure 4: Example of a policy entry ‘Universal Basic Services’ updated and completed through T1.3 of the MERGE project (Description tab)

Universal Basic Services

Description Case Study 1 Case Study 2

Affordable housing associations in the Netherlands

Although this example does not completely fit the definition of universal basic services due to its income eligibility criteria, it does provide informative inputs into the discussion of universal basic services in the context of housing. Indeed, this case study presents a large-scale housing services programme that is organised to meet the social needs of the population and has achieved financial stability. However, this system has also faced criticisms for leaving behind lower-middle-income households who are not eligible but often cannot afford housing in the regular housing market.

- **Case description**

The first housing associations (HAs) appeared in the Netherlands between 1850 and 1860 as cooperatives founded by well-off workers and employers, following an ideal of philanthropic capitalism. In 1901, the Housing Law marked an increasing state intervention by setting standards for housing quality and establishing a framework for government support to housing associations. Religious housing associations and local municipal housing associations started to appear. Following World War II, the government started to subsidise HAs to construct a large number of social rental dwellings. After the 1980s, government subsidies started to disappear as HAs achieved financial independence and broadened their activities towards other social projects, public purpose building and commercial real estate. However, with this movement of marketisation and neo-liberalisation of the HAs, accusations of fraud and mismanagement started to appear. In 2011, the central government took back control of HAs and in discussion with the European Commission, new housing allocation rules were established to target more socially disadvantaged populations (Joris, 2017).

Today, Dutch Housing Associations are private, nonprofit enterprises that manage around 75% of the rental homes in the Netherlands and 35% of the entire housing stock. HAs are required to lease 80% of their vacant units to low-income families and 10% to intermediate-income families. Rents are determined through a regulated point system and are maintained below market levels. Rents depend on the market value of the property, the dwelling characteristics (such as size, facilities or energy efficiency). Rents can only increase at a set, predetermined rate each year (Sainz, 2023).

The fund model of HAs is sustained by rental income and proceeds from selective property sales, which are reinvested in new housing developments, renovations and neighbourhood regeneration projects. It does not rely on direct government subsidies but instead on structures that allow HAs to secure credit at a very favourable rate (Sainz, 2023).

One of those structures, the Central Fund for Social Housing (CFV), is the primary financial regulator for HAs. It strictly supervises the activities, financial management and governance of the housing associations.

- **Policy impact:**

Housing associations provide good quality affordable housing by renting out 2.3 million dwellings. In 2014, around 85% of the lower-income group renting their accommodation benefited from a regulated rent below 700 euros. For the lower middle-income group and the middle middle-income group, this was around 50 and 30%, respectively (Schilder & Scherpenisse, 2018).

The Dutch model for affordable housing associations has been regarded as a successful approach to ensuring both social objectives and financial autonomy and stability.

However, in recent years, the housing supply in the Netherlands has not kept up with demographic trends, and the housing cost overburden rate reached 9.5% in 2023 (higher than the EU average of 8.9%). Although rents in affordable housing remain capped, the increasing needs have left some parts of the population unable to access those houses. However, this issue is not specific to the social sector but to the whole housing market.

Nevertheless, this example presents some interesting findings for discussion on delivering universal basic services, namely:

- Achieving financial stability without relying on direct government subsidies is possible. The use of commercial practices to support social objectives can serve as an example of innovative financial strategies to support public goods.
- The importance of good governance and a robust regulatory framework to maintain the integrity of the system and ensure good service delivery is crucial, especially in cases where the risk of moral hazard is high.
- Stricter income limits for allocation can create a process of *residualisation* (increasing concentration of lower income groups in a shrinking social rental sector) and leave behind those households with slightly higher income (Joris, 2017). This process also leads to increasing spatial segregation and perceptions of unfairness from some native Dutch citizens (Sainz, 2023). This highlights even more the advantages of a system that would truly be universal.
- The access to universal access to services is very much dependent on the quantity of supply of such services. One of the major issues of the housing market in the Netherlands is that the supply of residential buildings in the last decade has failed to follow the increased demand. For households eligible for social housing, this has led to increasing waiting times to access such housing. For low-income households ineligible to social housing, this has left them with hard-to-find and pricey options on the regular liberalised housing market (Geis, 2023).

This case study was added as part of the MERGE research project (funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, grant agreement N° 101132524).

Sources

- Geis, A. (2023). Housing supply in the Netherlands: the road to more affordable living.
- Joris, H. (2017). Reregulation and residualization in Dutch social housing: A critical evaluation of new policies. *Critical Housing Analysis*, 4(1), 31-39.
- Saiz, A. (2023). The global housing affordability crisis: Policy options and strategies. *MIT Center for Real Estate Research Paper*, (23/01).
- Schilder, F., & Scherpenisse, R. (2018). *Policy and practice: affordable housing in the Netherlands*. The Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.

Figure 5: Example of a policy entry ‘Universal Basic Services’ updated and completed through T1.3 of the MERGE project (Case Study tab)

4.4. Acknowledgement of funding

Acknowledgement of the specific contribution made under MERGE has been added under each policy entry. Additionally, the MERGE logo is included in the Funding subsection of the website’s ‘About’ section.

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Date: 26.06.2024

5. Beyond GDP streams

In addition to the tasks mentioned above, we aimed to provide an overview of the different streams and frameworks that co-exist in the Beyond GDP space. While these have become increasingly popular in recent years, they are still frequently misunderstood, particularly beyond academic spheres. With the goal of clarifying the content of these concepts and providing a definition that is accessible to the general public, we developed a summary table building on the sister projects inputs that shows how the different streams can be characterised in relation to four key areas: GDP, wellbeing, inclusion and sustainability. To leverage the research conducted in the sister projects, we made an effort to merge WISE Horizons 'overview of de-growth, green growth, and a-growth table', with the ToBe 'summary of alternative economic initiatives' table. We further included Sustainable Development as outlined in the 2030 Agenda, as this is a main guiding framework for the SPES project.

Table 2 presents such summary table.

Table 2: Conceptual differences between Beyond-GDP streams across key wellbeing dimensions.

Beyond GDP streams		Relation to economic growth / GDP	Relation to wellbeing (wellbeing today)	Relation to inclusion (wellbeing for all)	Relation to sustainability (wellbeing in the future)
Green growth		Economic growth can be (absolutely and comprehensively) 'decoupled' from environmental pressures. GDP is a welfare indicator.	Economic growth increases human wellbeing in the Global North and South. Wellbeing today is tied to economic prosperity and environmental quality.	Economic growth across all countries as a precondition for wellbeing. Policies can support distributing the benefits of growth across regions and populations.	Emphasis on supply side efficiency measures (ex: support of green technologies) and market mechanisms to ensure future well-being.
Post - growth	A-growth	Non-economic outcomes are prioritised above economic growth (the economy is a means to an end). Agnostic to decoupling. GDP is not suitable measure of welfare. Indifference to GDP.	Wellbeing is pursued regardless of its impact on economic growth. The focus is on addressing major societal challenges (e.g. transgressed planetary boundaries, poverty, unemployment).	Equity is prioritised over the scale of the economy. Building economies that are distributive by design.	Environmental transition and sustainability of social systems are pursued regardless of their impacts on economic growth, emphasis both on supply and demand side.
	De-growth	Economic growth is limited by planetary boundaries. No proof of absolute decoupling: a reduction in material and energy throughput is necessary.	Wellbeing is a priority, and growth does not support wellbeing past a threshold. Focus on sufficiency.	Reduction of resource consumption and use in high income countries to allow space for lower income countries to expand, where necessary.	Emphasis on demand side sufficiency measures and direct regulation for addressing basic needs of current and future generations and reducing environmental footprint.

		GDP is a poor indicator for societal progress.		Deconstruction of the 'colonialist growth paradigm' as an approach to development.	
Post-development	Alternative ways to fulfil human needs within planetary boundaries. Decoupling is infeasible. Decentring the focus on GDP to construct other indicators.	Transformation of society rather than development, and decentring economic growth from the definition of both economy and social life. Appreciation of Indigenous and local knowledge and values.		Focus on grassroots movements, demonstrates the impacts of social exclusion and environmental inequalities. Builds bridges between the Global South and the Global North for an ecological and civilizational transition.	Challenges the notion that constant economic development is sustainable. Sustainability by honouring cultural visions and transformative initiatives from around the world.
Sustainable development	Sustained economic growth (as long as it is inclusive and sustainable) is seen as essential for prosperity. Embedded in SDG8, which includes an indicator on annual growth rate of real GDP per capita.	Wellbeing mostly linked to health and material wellbeing. Ending poverty and hunger, as a means to ensure that everyone can live with dignity.		Several dimensions of inclusion (such as political, financial, and social) as part of the definition of what sustainable development means.	Sustainability becomes a core component of development. Includes the perspective of protecting the needs of present and future generations.

6. Limitations and ways forward

We acknowledge that the Sustainable Prosperity Database has been developed over the years and is based on various grants, including the 1.5-Degree Lifestyles project, a significant grant that led to a review and expansion of the database, primarily focused on sufficiency policy. Therefore, the existing database entries reflected a policy focus closer to the output and consumption side, rather than, for example, the production side and industry. In the selection and new additions of policies covered by this task, we made an effort to ensure a balanced package of consumption and production-focused policies.

Given the timeframe for Task 1.3, the aim of this exercise was not to find evidence for a comprehensive list of policies that contribute to an economy that delivers sustainable and inclusive wellbeing. Rather, Task 1.3 has made a start at complementing the database by adding case study descriptions and policy evaluation results focusing on the 15 most transformational policies towards advancing sustainable and inclusive wellbeing, within the project timeline. This work serves as an important foundation for tasks that follow it in the MERGE project, such as Task 1.4 'Summary and review of the linkages between indicators, models, sustainability goals, and policies' and tasks under WP4 'Usable and acceptable frameworks and indicators' and WP6 'Policy deep dives'.

Annex

Basic Income

Universal basic income is an income support mechanism, high enough to ensure a material existence and participation in society and typically intended to reach all (or a very large portion of the population) with no (or minimal) conditions (Francese, Prady, 2018). However, there is no single established definition, and very different income-support programs have been labelled "universal basic income". Bidanure in "The Political Theory of Universal Basic Income" (2019) identifies five features that generally remain constant from one proposal to the next: it is 1) a recurrent payment, rather than a one-off grant, 2) paid in cash, 3) universal, 4) unconditional, and 5) paid on an individual basis, rather than on a household basis.

Case studies

In the EU or elsewhere, no country has put in place a universal basic income, even though many pilot programs have been tested all over the world. As of January 2024, the [Stanford Basic Income Lab](#) had identified 192 past or present basic income (defined as regular, unconditional cash payments) experiments around the world. Among the six examples implemented in the EU, we focus on two of them: the Basic Income Experiment in Finland and the B-MINCOME experiment in Barcelona, Spain.

1 – Basic Income Experiment in Finland

- **Description of the program:**

In 2017–2018, the Finnish Government launched a Basic Income experiment, implemented by Kela, the Social Insurance Institution of Finland. The experiment involved 2,000 unemployed individuals aged 25 to 58 who received a monthly payment of €560 unconditionally and without the need to register. These participants were randomly selected from those receiving labour market support or basic unemployment allowances in November 2016 for reasons other than a temporary layoff. Basic income was paid to the experimental group free of charge for two years, and income from work or self-employment did not reduce the benefit (Kangas et al., 2020). The primary objective was to assess the employment effects of basic income, with secondary evaluations focused on wellbeing.

- **Policy impact:**

The employment rate for basic income recipients showed a slight improvement compared to the control group, although other employment measures were implemented simultaneously, making it difficult to isolate the effects of basic income alone (Verho, Hämäläinen, & Kanninen, 2022).

Survey-based evaluations showed significant positive impacts on the wellbeing of basic income recipients (Kangas et al., 2020). Compared to the control group, recipients reported higher life satisfaction, reduced mental strain, depression, sadness, and loneliness, likely due to the financial stability provided by the consistent monthly income. They also had a more positive perception of their cognitive abilities, such as memory, learning, and concentration, and felt more confident in their economic wellbeing and future employment prospects. Recipients exhibited higher levels of trust in other people, societal institutions, and their ability to influence their circumstances, and they experienced less bureaucratic burden related to social benefits and financial management (Kangas, Jauhiainen, Simanainen, & Ylikännö, 2021).

The stability and predictability of basic income contributed to mental and emotional benefits, suggesting that basic income can address diverse social needs. Recipients felt encouraged to seek and retain employment, even in low-paid and insecure jobs (as by design, the basic income payment was guaranteed for 2 years regardless of income from work), indicating that basic income could potentially support labour market participation without the negative incentives often associated with traditional welfare programs. Future policies should consider these wellbeing benefits and the potential for basic income to reduce bureaucratic complexity in social benefit systems.

2 – B-MINCOME pilot project in Barcelona, Spain

- **Description of the project:**

The B-MINCOME combined a minimum guaranteed income with active social policies in deprived urban areas of Barcelona. The project was part of the EU's Urban Innovative Actions programme and lasted 36 months, with 24 months of intervention and evaluation from November 2017 to October 2019. It provided up to 950 vulnerable households with a monetary transfer (Municipal Inclusion Support or SMI), among which 531 were also recipients of four active policies in the areas of: training and employment (152), entrepreneurship in the social, solidarity and cooperative economy (99), housing reforms for refurbishing and renting rooms (10), and a community participation

program (270). Although the B-MINCOME was given at the household level rather than the individual level, it is still a very close example of what a UBI would be in theory as it was designed and supported by UBI advocates and is used in the literature as a famous case study of a UBI experimentation.

- **Policy impact:**

Impact evaluation of the B-MINCOME initiative showed that it increased people's levels of general wellbeing as well as their financial wellbeing, with a significant effect in all participation modalities or groups. It reduced severe material deprivation by 8% on average. It reduced the probability of 'going to bed hungry' by around 10% and the reduction in worry about not having enough food by 18% on average. No statistically significant changes, however, were observed in terms of energy poverty or housing insecurity attributable to the B-MINCOME (Torrens & Villareal, 2019).

No significant improvements were observed either in terms of participants' ability to pay an unexpected expense of €750 with their own resources, which was expected, as SMI is designed to cover basic needs and not to save money.

Receiving SMI did not reduce significantly participation in employment of the recipients compared to the control group when given unconditionally. Some small reduction was, however, observed when SMI was combined with active policies or had conditionalities attached to it, due to a *lock-in effect* with people lacking time to look for work from taking part in the policy. No significant impact was found on the probability of having quality work, deciding to open a business or undergoing training for adults.

No statistically significant changes were observed in the self-perceived health of B-MINCOME participants. However, there was a 9-point reduction in the risk of mental illness, and the quality of sleep improved substantially for participating households, likely due to reduced stress from alleviated financial difficulties.

B-MINCOME households also showed a higher probability of engaging in social leisure activities compared to the control group. However, there were no significant changes in participation in civil society groups or organizations.

Life satisfaction increased by 27% from the start to the end of the project. Participants who received additional training and employment support were 9.5% happier than the average.

Conclusions of the impact evaluation highlight the importance of:

1. **Comprehensive Support:** initiatives providing not only financial assistance but also support in skill development and access to education can further enhance wellbeing and employability.
2. **Tailored Approach:** Personalise active policies to match participants' skills and interests to maximise effectiveness and attractiveness for future job prospects.
3. **Continuity and Expansion:** Consider extending and continuing support beyond initial phases to prevent participants from returning to financial insecurity, addressing long-term needs effectively.

Project website: [B-MINCOME - Combining guaranteed minimum income and active social policies in deprived urban areas | UIA - Urban Innovative Actions \(uia-initiative.eu\)](#)

Other Policy Entries

To ally environmental and social action, the idea of ecological income financed by taxes on undesirable environmental consumption has been put forward:

- Ecological Basic Income

References

On the Finnish case

Kangas, O., Jauhiainen, S., Simanainen, M., & Ylikännö, M. (2020). *Suomen perustulokokeilun arviointi* (Raportteja ja muistioita 2020:15). Sosiaali- ja terveystieteiden tutkimuskeskus. <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-00-9890-2>

Kangas, O., Jauhiainen, S., Simanainen, M., & Ylikännö, M. (Eds.). (2021). *Experimenting with Unconditional Basic Income: Lessons from the Finnish BI Experiment 2017-2018*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839104855>

[Verho, J., Hämäläinen, K., & Kanninen, O. \(2022\). Removing welfare traps: Employment responses in the Finnish basic income experiment. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 14\(1\), 501-522.](#)

On the Barcelona case (Spain)

[Torrens, L., & Villareal, J. \(2019\). Report on the preliminary results of the B-MINCOME project \(2017-18\): Combining a guaranteed minimum income and active social policies in deprived urban areas of Barcelona. Planning and Innovation Department, Area of Social Rights, Barcelona City Council.](#)

On universal basic income

Bidadanure, J. U. (2019). The political theory of universal basic income. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 22, 481-501. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-050317-070954>

Francese, M., & Prady, D. (2018) Back to Basics: what is Universal Basic Income? *Finance & Development*, 0055(004), A011. Retrieved Aug 22, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781484386194.022.A011>

Free or low-fare public transport

Free or low fare public transport is a measure to make public transport more attractive and affordable, as it allows all users to use public transport unlimited and free (or low) of charge. In other words, free fare public transport means that public transport users do not contribute to funding the service directly through the payment of a fare.

The strengthening of public transport services and infrastructure should also remain an overarching principle when discussing free fare (International Association of Public Transport, 2023).

Case studies

Free transport has been implemented in over 50 EU cities, including the Estonian capital of Tallinn and in Templin, Germany. The following case studies focus on the two cases of free fare public transport: Luxembourg, the only country to have implemented nation-wide free public transport, and the city of Dunkirk in France; and two cases of low-fare public transport: Germany (national level), and the city of Bonn in Germany.

1 – Free universal public transport in Luxembourg

- **Description of the project:**

On February 29, 2020, Luxembourg became the first nation in the world to make all public transit entirely free at the point of use. Buses, trams and trains became free to ride without the need for a ticket. With the measure, the government aims to have 20% more passengers on public transport within five years in a country where the car density is one of the highest in the world.

- **Policy impact:**

Authors: Kormann da Silva, N.,
Chevallier, R., Bremer, O., Brosio, M.,
Frieling, M., Hirvilammi, T., Hynynen,
K., Kilpi, J., Rannikko, A., & Zinutti, M.

Date: 26.06.2024

A simulation study that compared the outcomes after the intervention with a benchmarking scenario where public transport was still not free found that the policy brought significant increases in Passenger Kilometre (PKT) and Hours Travelled (PHT) for Public Transport. At the same time, the study found that the overall impact was not big enough to strongly reduce congestion levels (Bigi, Schwemmler, & Viti, 2023).

The study concludes that to have a positive impact, 'free transport' policies must be complemented by policies addressing other disadvantages of using public transport (such as overcrowding, delayed or cancelled trains). Indeed, another study showed that to increase the use of buses or trains, attributes such as reliable services, in-vehicle travel time, number of transfers, and feeling safe are the most important (Maciejewska, Boussauw, Kębtowski, & Van Acker, 2023).

2 – Fare-free public transport in Dunkirk, France

- **Description of the project:**

In 2018, Dunkirk and surrounding regions introduced a universal free-fare public transport (FFPT) on the 'DK'BUS' bus network, alongside an ongoing restructuring of the network serving the Dunkirk urban agglomeration and surrounding area. The project began in 2014 with a series of public consultation meetings on the policy proposal. Simultaneously, investments were made to improve the transport network capacity and connectivity from 2016. The reduced revenue from public transport ticket sales was met by increasing the 'versement mobilité' (VM), an employer contribution to mobility, paid by all companies that employ at least 11 employees (European Commission, 2021).

- **Impact evaluation:**

The overall objective was to increase the total number of bus journeys by more than 10% by 2020. An initial evaluation for the period from January to May 2019, compared to the same period in 2017, found that the number of trips increased by 85% and that bus use increased by 65% during the week and by 120% at weekends. A survey of 2,000 users found that the network was being used more intensively than before by existing users and that new users comprised 50% of all users. Almost half of new users (48%) had moved to bus from private cars, and the overall modal shift for all passengers from car to bus was 24% (European Commission, 2021).

The Dunkirk example confirms the importance of investing in service capacity and quality in addition to cancelling fees.

3 – 9-Euro-Ticket in Germany

- **Case description:**

In spring 2022, the German federal government introduced measures in response to the 2022 cost-of-living crisis. Among these was a nationwide local public transport ticket priced at 9 euros per month. This special offer was valid exclusively during June, July, and August 2022, providing unlimited travel on all local and regional public transport services throughout Germany. The initiative was partly motivated as a response to the war in Ukraine, which led to a significant increase in fossil fuel prices. In response, several countries in Europe, including Germany, decided to provide sustainable transport alternatives.

- **Policy impact:**

Researchers conducted a natural experiment using a three-wave survey and a smartphone-based semi-passive travel diary utilizing waypoint tracking (Loder et al., 2024). A total of 2,316 participants were recruited, with 907 agreeing to participate in the tracking. Most of these participants were in the Munich metropolitan region and were users of the 9-Euro-Ticket. Among them, 1,454 respondents completed the three-wave survey, while 684 respondents completed the survey and provided travel behaviour data using the smartphone app.

The policy was extremely successful, with 52 million tickets sold. Researchers discovered that public transport use notably increased, especially among customers using the 9-Euro-Ticket who did not previously have a travel pass. Regular public transport use rose from 29% before the introduction of the 9-Euro-Ticket to 38% during its availability, and stabilized at 32% after its conclusion. Approximately 20% of 9-Euro-Ticket holders substituted some private transport trips with public transport during the ticket's duration. Tracking data revealed that local public transport travel distances decreased by 37% for those exclusively using the 9-Euro-Ticket and by 30% for travel pass holders after the ticket's availability. Furthermore, discontinuing the 9-Euro-Ticket resulted in around one-third fewer active public transport users compared to those who had the 9-Euro-Ticket but no previous travel pass.

4 – Bonner climate ticket in Bonn, Germany

- **Case description:**

Authors: Kormann da Silva, N.,
Chevallier, R., Bremer, O., Brosio, M.,
Frieling, M., Hirvilammi, T., Hynynen,
K., Kilpi, J., Rannikko, A., & Zinutti, M.

Date: 26.06.2024

Bonn, an international UN campus and self-proclaimed climate capital, declared a climate emergency in 2019 and joined a federally funded “Lead City” project aimed at enhancing air quality. A primary objective of this initiative is to decrease reliance on private motorised transport while bolstering public transportation. As part of these efforts, the city introduced a "climate ticket" in 2019, allowing consumers to buy an annual 365 € pass for unlimited travel on local public transport.

- **Policy impact:**

A quantitative survey involving 1,315 climate ticket users, along with multiple regression analyses, confirmed that the climate ticket succeeded in attracting more customers to buses and trams, indicating a noticeable modal shift during the period of its implementation.

The Bonner climate ticket resulted in fewer car trips and reduced congestion on major traffic routes, with public transport being the most preferred mode of transport during the ticket period (Hahn et al., 2024).

Users of the climate ticket were generally very satisfied with the offer and expressed a desire for it to be made permanent. However, individuals not in employment evaluated the measure less positively than those who were employed full-time.

Women showed a higher willingness to use public transport and rated the climate ticket more favourably than men.

Climate ticket users identified opportunities for improvement in the integration with tickets from other transport associations, particularly in rural areas. The findings highlight that, besides affordability, ensuring travel time and reliability are crucial factors. Moreover, expanding eligibility criteria, coverage areas, and enhancing connectivity services are essential.

Other Policy Entries

To complement this policy, initiatives that discourage the use of cars (particularly with low passenger numbers) and encourage the uptake of active travel modes are important. Related policy entries on the Sustainable Prosperity website include:

- Ban on car driving through city centres
- Congestion charge zones for individual car use
- Increase subsidies for public transportation

- Public digital platform for multimodal traffic
- Passenger rights in multimodal transport

References

Bigi, F., Schwemmler, N. P., & Viti, F. (2023). Evaluating the impact of Free Public Transport using agent-based modeling: The case-study of Luxembourg. In *hEART 2023: 11th Symposium of the European Association for Research in Transportation*, September 6-8, 2023.

European Commission. (2021, April 28). *Free passenger transport – exploring the benefits and disadvantages*. EU Urban Mobility Observatory. https://urban-mobility-observatory.transport.ec.europa.eu/resources/case-studies/free-passenger-transport-exploring-benefits-and-disadvantages_en

Hahn, A., Pakusch, C., & Stevens, G. (2024). Was the low-fare public transport in Bonn a success? An evaluation of the climate ticket users and lessons for transportation companies. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 15, 101158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2024.101158>

International Association of Public Transport. (2023, April 19). *Full free fare public transport: Objectives and alternatives*. UITP. <https://www.uitp.org/publications/full-free-fare-public-transport-objectives-and-alternatives/>

Kębtowski, W. (2020). Why (not) abolish fares? Exploring the global geography of fare-free public transport. *Transportation*, 47(6), 2807–2835. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-019-09986-6>

Loder, A., Cantner, F., Adenaw, L., Nachtigall, N., Ziegler, D., Gotzler, F., Siewert, M. B., Wurster, S., Goerg, S., Lienkamp, M., & Bogenberger, K. (2024). Observing Germany's nationwide public transport fare policy experiment "9-Euro-Ticket" – Empirical findings from a panel study. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 15, 101148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2024.101148>

Maciejewska, M., Boussauw, K., Kębtowski, W., & Van Acker, V. (2023). Assessing public transport loyalty in a car-dominated society: The case of Luxembourg. *Journal of Public Transportation*, 25, 100061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubtr.2023.100061>

Universal Job Guarantee

A universal job guarantee provides jobs — and wages — to people who are unable to find work on their own. In theory, a universal job guarantee could provide stable, full-time employment, address unemployment, enhance economic productivity and reinforce price stability.

Case studies

Universal job guarantee experiments are scarce. However, some examples of implementation can be found. Below, we explore the cases in Marienthal, Austria, and in Greece.

1 – Universal Job Guarantee in Marienthal, Austria

- **Case description:**

This project is designed by Oxford University economists and run by the Austrian Public Employment Service. Structural unemployment in Austria has been rising since the 1980s and was compounded by the COVID-19 pandemic. When the Marienthal job guarantee pilot began in August 2020, roughly one in five unemployed people in Lower Austria had been looking for a job for more than a year (Oxford University, 2020). The scheme offers a universal guarantee of a properly paid job (paying at least the minimum wage, bringing people's incomes above the level of social benefits) to every resident who has been unemployed for more than 12 months. Participants start with a two-month preparation process, including one-to-one training, counselling and, for those who need it, support from experienced social workers, doctors and psychologists. They are then helped to find a suitable and subsidised private sector job or supported to create a job based on their skills and their knowledge of their community's needs. All participation is voluntary; no sanctions are involved.

The Public Employment Service of Lower Austria funded the €7.4 million project, which is economically viable as a year of unemployment costs about €30,000 per person, while the project costs €29,841 per participant. Additionally, the project's employment activities were expected to generate around €383,000 in revenue (Oxford University, 2020)

- **Policy impact:**

An impact evaluation of the programme by Oxford University showed that, at the individual level, the universal job guarantee significantly improved the economic wellbeing of participants, including their outcomes in relation to employment, income, and economic security (Kasy & Lehner, 2023). This was notable since non-participants were still eligible for unemployment benefits. Significant positive effects were also observed in relation to non-economic outcomes such as time use, activity level, social contacts, sense of collective purpose, and social recognition. At a municipality-level, a large reduction in unemployment was observed, primarily due to a near-elimination of long-term unemployment. There was no increase in short-term unemployment, indicating no negative spillovers. The initial positive effects on economic wellbeing and employment persisted over time, suggesting long-term benefits.

Participants who joined the programme at a later stage showed similar improvements as the first group, but some measures, such as subjective wellbeing, social status, and social inclusion, showed slightly larger improvements compared to the initial experimental group, possibly due to anticipation effects.

The results of this pilot project suggest that the job guarantee is a promising policy instrument to reduce long-term unemployment and to improve the wellbeing of people who are unemployed.

2 – Kinofelis programme in Greece

- **Case description:**

The Kinofelis programme was launched by the Greek government in response to high unemployment and long-term unemployment rates. It offers long-term unemployed individuals eight months of work on municipal projects at the minimum wage, including social security contributions. The programme was founded by the European Social Fund and was implemented by the Greek Ministry of Labour. The International Labour Organisation provided technical support.

The program prioritised the long-term unemployed, those who did not receive unemployment benefits, and specific groups such as youth under 30, the unemployed over 55, single-parent families, university graduates, and unemployed farmers across 17 municipalities. Participants were employed for five months during Phases One and Two (2011-2015), and eight months during Phase Three (2016-2020). They received the minimum wage (EUR 780/month, as of April 2023), full health care benefits, parental leave, and retirement contributions. Participants were engaged in various types of work,

including work in the following sectors: culture, sports, environment, public sanitation, administrative services, economic development, construction, repairs, renovations, health, welfare, and social services. Since 2016, participants could also receive optional IT training.

- **Policy impact:**

From 2015 to 2018, the programme reached 200,000 participants, with 45,000 participants in 2018 alone (Antonopoulos, 2023; ILO & European Commission, 2018). A large proportion of beneficiaries assessed that Kinofelis may help them advance their professional life, because it “helped them to go back to a work discipline (82.2%), acquire a working schedule in everyday life (80.3%), improve access to professional networks (75.3%), and develop a new sense of professional self-worth (84.4%)” (ILO, 2018)

The survey amongst participants at the start and the end of the programme showed that participants reported a higher sense of purpose, perceived health, and better social relations. They also reported lower substance abuse and lower use of violence. However, findings suggest that for these benefits to last in the long term, participants would need to find other work after Kinofelis (given the temporary nature of the programme) (ILO, 2018).

Beneficiaries primarily used the additional income to increase consumption of food and everyday products, take breaks or travel to visit relatives, and repay bills and tax instalments, rather than debt repayment or luxury consumption. Many beneficiaries invested in technologies and goods to improve their job prospects.

According to the ILO, although the Kinofelis program is only temporary and was not found to have a substantial effect on employment, it did have a positive impact on “shifting the most vulnerable groups of the unemployed into workers that are ‘work-ready’ and could find work if the conditions in the Greek labour market were to improve” (ILO, 2018). Overall, beneficiaries considered Kinofelis a much more effective way to re-enter the labour market than training only.

Resources

Antonopoulos, R. (2023). *Has the time for a European job guarantee policy arrived?* (Levy Economics Institute Working Paper No. 1022). Levy Economics Institute of Bard College. https://www.levyinstitute.org/pubs/wp_1022.pdf

[ILO and European Commission \(EC\). \(2018\). Kinofelis Programme Implementation Manual. pg 11.](#)

International Labour Organization (2018). Getting back to work: a study of the social impacts of Kinofelis Development. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/documents/publication/wcms_623960.pdf

Kasy, M., & Lehner, L. (2023). *Employing the unemployed of Marienthal: Evaluation of a guaranteed job program* (CESifo Working Paper No. 10394). CESifo Group. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4431385>

Oxford University. (2020, November 20). *World's first universal jobs guarantee experiment starts in Austria*. <https://www.ox.ac.uk/news/2020-11-02-world-s-first-universal-jobs-guarantee-experiment-starts-austria>

High Inheritance Tax

Wealth accumulation and inequality have been sharply growing in the past years. A considered part of this wealth is inherited, with estimates indicating that inheritances constitute 30% to 60% of overall wealth in Western countries (Piketty and Zucman, 2015).

These trends underscore the importance of inheritance taxes, which are levied on money or assets that are inherited. High inheritance taxes can help break through path-dependencies and create more equal starting positions within the economic sphere. They can also be used to finance essential services and social security independently of economic growth.

Case studies

When it comes to inheritance taxation, there is no universally accepted model for determining an optimal tax rate. The design of inheritance taxes across countries is very heterogeneous: while some countries have even opted for a 0% inheritance tax, such as Australia and Sweden, there are countries that have implemented significantly higher rates. Examples of countries with the highest inheritance taxes include (Redonda 2017; Jestl 2021; OECD 2021):

- **Japan:** Inheritance taxation was introduced in Japan in 1950, and tax rates range from 10% up to 55% in the country.
- **South Korea:** As well as in Japan, South Korea has inheritance taxes in place since 1950, which apply to both resident donors' worldwide assets and to non-resident donors' local assets. South Korea has a maximum tax rate of 50%. In

general, estates are taxed at progressive rates. Like many other countries, spouses benefit from a more generous tax treatment, and business assets are also subject to some sort of preferential treatment.

- **France:** the French taxation scheme has been evolving over time, with an initial flat rate on wealth transfers since the French Revolution to a more progressive scheme from the beginning of the XX century on. Nowadays, France has tax classes with different progressivity depending on the relationship between the testator and the beneficiary and the value of inherited assets: class I: 5-45%, class II: 35-45%, class III: 55%, class IV: 60%.
- **United States:** Unlike the other examples listed here, the US taxes the transfer of wealth not only at the federal level but also at other tiers of government, such as the state level. The inheritance tax rate depends on the value of total inherited assets only, varying from 18% to 40%.
- **United Kingdom:** Inheritance taxation has been a long-time discussion topic in the UK, which has adopted rather a flat rate of 40%.

Policy impact and evaluation

The impacts of inheritance taxation are complex, as the design of inheritance tax can take different forms, and the whole taxation regime also influences its outcomes. There is vast theoretical literature on this topic, but the number of empirical studies is more limited. Some of the most explored impacts relate to individual's behaviour to inheritance and inheritance taxation (e.g. how it may affect family business), distributional effects, and tax revenue.

The OECD (2021) lists some results that are expected from inheritance taxation:

Enhance equality of opportunity: empirical studies have shown that inheritance plays a strong role in wealth persistence across generations. A tax on inherited wealth can help break down the concentration of wealth and levelling the playing field.

Reduce inequality over time: the paper suggests that a tax exemption threshold that allows small inheritances to be passed on free of tax, combined with a progressive inheritance tax rate schedule, may reduce absolute and relative wealth inequality. Moreover, the study also suggests that, given the negative externalities from wealth concentration, inheritance taxes have efficiency effects.

Behavioural impacts: The empirical literature on the impact of inheritance taxation on donors' wealth accumulation is very limited and generally shows negative, but small effects. When it comes to tax planning, evidence suggests that this behaviour is common, but strategies vary across countries and, in general, possibilities for tax planning have reduced the effective progressivity of inheritance taxes. Nevertheless, tax avoidance is not particular to inheritance taxation.

Policy entries in the database that relate to this policy:

- Shifting the tax burden from the private sphere to accumulated wealth
- Taxation of machinery owners
- Progressive property taxation
- Taxes on luxury goods
- Wealth tax
- Implementation of gift taxes
- Redistributive taxation

References

Jestl, S. (2021). Inheritance tax regimes: A comparison. *Public Sector Economics*, v. 45, n. 3. <https://doi.org/10.3326/pse.45.3.3>

OECD (2021). *Inheritance Taxation in OECD Countries*. OECD Tax Policy Studies, No. 28, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e2879a7d-en>.

Piketty, T., & Zucman, G. (2015). Wealth and inheritance in the long run. In A.B. Atkinson & F. Bourguignon (Eds.), *Handbook of Income Distribution* (pp. 1303-1368). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-59429-7.00016-9>

Redonda, A. (2017) Inheritance Taxation, Corporate Succession and Sustainability. CEP Discussion Note 2017/1: CEP – Council on Economic Policies. <https://www.cepweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CEP-DN-Inheritance-Taxes-Corporate-Succession-and-Sustainability-2.pdf>

Community Wealth Building

Community Wealth Building (CWB) is a people-centred approach to local economic development that emphasises democratic participation and local control and ownership. It offers an alternative to build inclusive and sustainable communities by redirecting wealth generated in the community back into the local economy (O'Neill, Guinan, 2019).

Case studies

CWB initiatives can take many different forms. This includes, for instance, non-profit and employee-owned businesses. Another example is the establishment of community development financial institutions, as is the case of Banco Palmas explored below. These initiatives usually involve collaboration and coordination of a wide range of actors, such as local governments, community leaders and associations, and labour unions.

In short, CWB offers a bottom-up alternative to local development. Below we review two case studies of how CWB has been implemented in different cities in the UK and in Brazil.

1 – Community Wealth Building in Preston, UK

- **Case description:**

The city of Preston in England has adopted CWB as a new approach to local economic development since 2013. The initiative, which is also known as the 'Preston Model', started as a collective effort of the local government, universities, housing providers, health facilities and others, to mobilise local assets and capacity such as skills, community networks, local institutions and firms, to drive economic development.

One of the main first initiatives involved re-designing procurement policy. New processes were put in place to support the development of local supply chains and businesses, such as the creation of a development network for cooperatives (the Preston Cooperative Development Network), and a regional Community and Cooperative Bank (Prinos, Manley 2022). Other policies focused on promoting investment in the local economy and improving recruitment and employment conditions (e.g. a living wage policy).

The goal of the Preston CWB strategy is to leverage existing economic wealth and social value to the benefit of the community, and by doing so, promote overall economic inclusion and wellbeing.

- **Policy impact:**

The Preston Model is widely recognised as a key example of Community Wealth Building. The initiative has yielded significant economic results; for instance, local anchor institutions in Preston increased their spending on local goods and services from 5% in 2013 to 18% in 2016/2017, redirecting over £70 million back into the Preston economy (CLES, 2019)

Looking at broader macroeconomic indicators also suggests improvements, although no direct causal link has been established. Notably, Preston's unemployment rate, which was above the average before the programme's implementation, fell below average after the Preston Model was introduced, and 4000 extra employees received the real living wage by 2018 (CLES, 2019). Additionally, in the same year, the city had moved out of the 20% most deprived local authority areas in the UK.

According to the Centre for Local Economic Strategies (CLES), other policy impacts have been strengthening connections between anchor institutions and the local economy and community, as well as fostering movement building. In this regard, anchor institutions involved in the Preston initiative have engaged in various activities focused on knowledge sharing, collaboration and capacity development.

It is important to note, however, that more recent trends indicate that the pace of progress in these areas has slowed (Whyman 2021). This slowdown might be in part due to a catching-up effect; however, it still underscores the need for continuous, long-term efforts focused on innovative economic strategies and enhanced community engagement.

2 – Banco Comunitário Palmas in Fortaleza, Brazil

- **Case description:**

Banco Palmas is the first community bank in Brazil, founded in 1998 by a local neighbourhood association in Fortaleza, a city in the northeast of the country. The community bank's objective is to provide financial services based on the principles of the solidarity economy, with ownership and management following a community-based approach. Most of the staff consists of volunteer residents from the community, and it follows a decentralised approach.

The bank focuses on four areas of the local productive chain: solidarity capital, sustainable production, solidarity consumption, and fair trade. It operates through various means, with key features including the provision of credit (in general microcredit) for production, trade, or services to those actors or businesses that are not able to access

“official” sources of finance due to bureaucracy, guarantor requirements, income levels, assets and others. It also offers solidarity funds for joint purchases, enabling businesses or individuals working in similar areas to collaborate and purchase inputs from suppliers using interest-free loans from the bank. In addition, Banco Palmas provides consumer credits focused on promoting local consumption.

Typical of such initiatives, shortly after Banco de Palmas began operating, it introduced its own currency – the “Palma” (Mostagi et al, 2019). This community currency works complementary to the national official currency. The use of local currency is a mechanism that supports that the “money” created stays within the community, as it is valid only for local consumption and trade.

- **Policy impact:**

Local (or social) currencies can help strengthen local businesses and activities as they promote keeping community resources within the community, rather than having them flow elsewhere. In the case of the “Palma” currency, while only 20% of people shopped within the community in the early years following the establishment of Banco de Palmas, a 2016 survey showed that this percentage had increased to 95% (Mostagi et al., 2019). By 2018, Instituto Palmas had delivered over 14 million Reais (more than 3.5 million Euros) in microcredit to individuals and businesses, with a focus on women who had previously lacked access to formal financial services (Ansorena et al, 2021).

Looking from a more qualitative perspective, the policy has positively impacted the community. According to Filho et al. (2012), Banco Palmas has increased residents’ self-esteem and the visibility of the neighbourhood, changing the way the community is perceived by the rest of the city. They also suggest that having the community bank has facilitated closer client-bank relations and may have resulted in a more favourable treatment of those seeking credit. Finally, a 2008 survey (10 years after the bank’s creation) also showed that 98% of respondents believed the creation of the bank had contributed to the growth of the community, and 90% said Banco Palmas had improved their quality of life (ibidem).

Following the example of the Banco Palmas, and with the support of the bank, many other community banks have been established across Brazil. A significant challenge faced by these community banks has been the lack of (national) regulation for these institutions, which were initially considered as social organisations rather than financial institutions.

This can limit their impact, e.g., by preventing community banks from collecting deposits. Therefore, it is crucial that different levels of governance work together in advancing institutional structures and frameworks to better support community wealth building initiatives.

- Official website: <https://bancopalmas.com/>

Related policy entries

- Reduction of bureaucratic barriers and accounting requirements for cooperatives
- Commons trusts

References

Ansorena, A, Diniz, E. H., Siqueira, E. S., Pozzebon, M. (2021). From Community Bank to Solidarity Fintech: The Case of Palmas e-Dinheiro in Brazil. In: Walker, T., McGaughey, J., Goubran, S., Wagdy, N. (eds) *Innovations in Social Finance*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72535-8_12

Centre for Local Economic Strategies (2019). *How we built community wealth in Preston: Achievements and lessons*. Centre for Local Economic Strategies. https://cles.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/CLES_Preston-Document_WEB-AW.pdf

França Filho, G. C. de, Silva Júnior, J. T., & Rigo, A. S. (2012). *Solidarity finance through community development banks as a strategy for reshaping local economies: Lessons from Banco Palmas*. *Revista de Administração*, 47(3), 500–515. <https://doi.org/10.5700/rausp1054>

Mostagi, N., Pires, L., Mahnic, C. & Santos, L. (2019). Banco Palmas: inclusão e desenvolvimento local. *Interações (Campo Grande)*. <https://doi.org/10.20435/inter.v0i0.1653>

O'Neill, M., Guinan, J. (2019). *The case for community wealth building*.

Prinos, I., Manley, J. (2022). The Preston Model: Economic Democracy, Cooperation, and Paradoxes in Organisational and Social Identification. *Sociological Research Online*, 28(3), 627-643. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13607804211069398>

Whyman, P. B. (2021). The Economics of the Preston Model. In: Manley, J., Whyman, P. B. (eds) *The Preston Model and Community Wealth Building*.

Cap on income or maximum pay differential

A cap on income sets an upper limit on the amount of income an individual or entity can earn within a certain period. A maximum pay differential can cap salaries so that the highest-paid citizen/employee would only earn a certain percentage more than the lowest-paid citizen/employee.

Case studies

In the EU, since 2012, France caps the gross annual wage of public companies' executives at 450 000 euros. This represents about 20 times the mean of the lowest salaries in public companies. In the Netherlands, the Balkenende standard is an unofficial salary cap for top executives in public and semi-public sectors, which states that no public official should earn more than the Prime Minister. While not a legally binding rule, the Balkenende standard serves as a benchmark for salary discussions and policy formulations in the Netherlands. To date, no impact evaluations of these policies have been published.

Indeed, case studies and evidence on caps on income or a maximum pay differential are limited: first, due to the small number of instances in which these policies have been implemented and second, due to the small number of empirical studies on existing cases. Nonetheless, case study examples include the following:

1 – Executive Compensation Cap Law in Israel

- **Case description:**

Since the introduction of the Compensation Capping Act in Israel in 2016, the compensation of financial firms' executives in Israel is limited to 35 times the compensation of the lowest-paid employee at the firm. It is the only case in the world of a cap on executives' compensation in non-state-owned firms. This law targets only certain types of financial firms: banks, insurance companies, investment firms, asset management firms and mutual funds.

- **Policy impact:**

The law was found to be successful in significantly cutting the compensation of financial firm executives. Although evidence on the effects of the law is limited, one study found that the legislation was not accompanied by weaker firm performance or increased risk-taking.

However, it resulted in a higher rate of executive turnover. This legislation also led to a narrowing of the pay disparity among top executives (Rozen, 2022)

Another study found that financial institutions affected by the cap (i.e. firms where executive pay was above the gap before the law) experienced significant abnormal positive returns shortly after the law was passed. The article attributes these positive returns to the perception that the law led to a reduction in rent extraction, meaning that the market viewed the cap as a way to reduce wasteful spending on executive pay, thereby increasing the overall value of the firm. This effect was stronger in firms with weaker corporate governance, which further supports this idea. The study also noted executive turnover following the passing of the law, but no significant negative market reactions (Mroczek-Dąbrowska & Shemesh, 2020).

2 – The Mondragon cooperative in Spain

- **Case description:**

Founded in the 1950s, the Mondragon cooperative is one of the most well-known examples of co-operative organisation and workers' self-management in the world. In 2018, the Mondragon group comprised around 100 firms and employed more than 81,000 workers (Reuten, 2021). The co-operatives in the group share a commitment to pay equity, which sets the maximum salary differential to a ratio of 1 to 9 in gross terms (around 1:6.5 after tax). This salary ratio was increased from its original 1:3 as pressures emerged from economic growth, increased demand for skilled managers and evolving attitudes. These changes were debated and decided with approval from the general assembly of worker members, and most cooperatives still maintain smaller ratios than those allowed. Performance bonuses are rarely used and are usually modest (Whyte & Whyte, 2014).

- **Policy impact:**

Generally, the Mondragon corporation is seen as a success story of a group that manages to be globally competitive while upholding cooperative principles. Mondragon experienced an impressive employment growth since the 1980s, with a total employment growth of 258% within its Spanish co-operatives (compared to 75% in Spain on average during the same period) (Reuten, 2021).

Survey and interview-based research indicate that Mondragon has faced some challenges in retaining capable managers, which they addressed by widening the pay scale. However, the principle was not given up altogether and senior managers in

Mondragon typically still earn less than their counterparts in conventional companies. While workers might transfer between different co-ops within the Mondragón network, virtually none return to traditional capitalist firms. This highlights a strong preference and loyalty to the cooperative model (Bowman & Stone, 2004).

The success of the Mondragon model suggests that a cooperative model, which includes a controlled wage differential, can be competitive and sustainable and create an attractive work environment in the long term (Redondo, Santa Cruz, & Rotger, 2011). The ability to attract and retain employees despite lower wage differentials for senior managers compared to conventional companies suggests that Mondragon offers other non-monetary benefits, such as a sense of ownership, recognition, community and a positive workplace culture (Bowman & Stone, 2004).

Related policy entries

The previous examples presented cases where maximum pay differentials were implemented. However, another option to address inequality and promote fair compensation structures can also be to set a cap on earnings, as was done in France for public companies' executive. This means that earnings at the lower hand can increase without repercussions on the maximum one can receive. Several policy options for caps on earnings could be implemented:

- Cap on profits
- Cap on salaries
- Instituting a maximum wage

References

Bowman, B., & Stone, B. (2004). Cooperativization on the mondragon model: Alternative to globalizing capitalism. *Humanity & society*, 28(3), 272-297.

Mroczek-Dąbrowska, K., & Shemesh, Y. (2020). (Re)-structuring the Ceo's compensation—the case of Israel. *Economics and Business Review*, 6(3), 105-117. <https://doi.org/10.18559/ebr.2020.3.6>

Redondo, G., Santa Cruz, I., & Rotger, J. M. (2011). Why Mondragon? Analyzing What Works in Overcoming Inequalities. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 17(3), 277-283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800410397806>

Reuten, G. (2021). *The employment performance of the Mondragon worker cooperatives 1983-2019* (Euricse Working Papers No. 118). SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3992304>

Rozen, M. (2022). *Effectiveness of executive compensation cap law: Evidence from Israel*. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4485490>

Whyte, W. F., & Whyte, K. K. (2014). *Making Mondragon: The growth and dynamics of the worker cooperative complex*. Cornell university press.

Encourage local food production

Over the past decades, local food systems (LFS) have been promoted by governments and civil society organisations as a lever for change towards more inclusive, resilient and sustainable food systems (Enthoven & Van den Broeck, 2021). Although there is no universal definition of LFS, the EU Joint Research Centre describes an LFS as “a food system in which foods are produced, processed and retailed within a defined geographical area (within a 20 to 100 km radius approximately)” (Kneafsey et al., 2013).

Case studies

Encouraging local food production and consumption can be achieved through various policies and initiatives. Policies to encourage local consumption can encompass education and awareness campaigns, labelling and certification programs, or creating local food hubs. Policies to encourage local production can be zoning and land use policies, tax incentives, subsidies and grants to local farmers and food producers or support to small-scale processing facilities. The case studies below present some of the options that are available to policymakers for promoting local food production and consumption:

1 – BioCanteen Transfer Network Initiative in France, Belgium, Italy, Romania, Portugal, Bulgaria and Greece

- **Case description:**

The BioCanteen Transfer Network Initiative is based on the experience of the Mouans-Sartoux city in France of successfully implementing a daily distribution of organic and locally produced meals that was then replicated in six European cities in Belgium, Italy, Romania, Portugal, Bulgaria and Greece, following the creation of a knowledge-sharing network.

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Date: 26.06.2024

The initial project was organised around five principles:

1. Sustainable Kitchen and Food Waste Management: Local, organic meals and reduced waste through staff training and cooking on demand.
2. Healthy Food Education: Canteen as a "food school" with education on portion sizes, cooking classes, gardening, and farm visits.
3. Sustainable Urban Planning: Integrated urban planning and municipal farm to support local food production.
4. Local Economy and Job Creation: Municipal land supports organic farms and creates up to 100 jobs.
5. Integrated Governance: creation of the Centre for Sustainable Food and Education, promoting sustainable agriculture, food processing, awareness, research, and communication.

Following the success of this first experience, a network of cities was created as part of Urbact, the European Territorial Cooperation programme that aims to foster sustainable integrated urban development in cities across Europe. As part of this network project, project leaders organised a three-day transnational meeting dedicated to good practices for project coordinators and school chefs.

In Troyan, Bulgaria, a municipal farm was built to provide canteens with local, organic products. The overall structure is made of three greenhouse tunnels of 200 sqm each with an irrigation system, a hall, an inventory storage, two refrigeration chambers and a preparation room. A farmer was recruited, and a step-by-step approach was adopted starting the plantation of a selection of crops in December 2020 which was expanded over time. The National Food Agency was contacted to certify the production.

In Rosignano Marittimo, Italy, the context was vastly different than the one in Mouans Sartroux as the canteen scheme relied on a delegation to private services. Thus, the focus went to translating best practices to set this specific setting with first the launch in November 2020 of an online platform mapping the local organic farms that could become potential tenders. Then the city requires its catering companies to source from local producers when possible and increase their share of organic products. To compensate higher costs of local products, the city started to sort and weight daily waste to better organise menus based on children's taste and increase the use of vegetable. The

city also started educative activities for children such as school gardens delivered by kitchen staff.

In Torres Vedras, Portugal, the city's objective was to increase the share of local and organic produce in canteens, in continuation to a previous program for sustainable food at school which aimed to get products only from local suppliers. This city wanted to use its public procurements to support the installation and work of local organic farmers but was facing the legal issues that 1) while organic certification can be used as a selection criterion, local production is not one, and 2) public contracts are limited to a set number of years with one company. Moreover, in the city, food distribution to canteens was divided between public and private institutions. The city overcame the first hurdle by establishing a new selection criterion, Freshness, valorising short transfers from the farm to the school kitchen. They also included special provision for organic food in tenders for schools managed by the municipality and in contracts with private caterers.

In LAG Pays des Condurses in Belgium and in Trikala in Greece, the context was again different as there were no canteens previously, and the objective was re-implementing such a scheme in a context when citizens do not have a culture for it. In Pays des Condurses, a training centre for unemployed people was already delivering partial canteen services to school. However, since authorities do not financially support the price of the meal it was seen by parents as an additional cost compared to them preparing sandwiches for their children. Following BioCanteens practices, the city implemented a social tariff targeting children benefiting from public help. A web service was also created to allow parents to book meals in advance. In Trikala, Greece, primary and secondary school students go to school from 8 AM to 2 PM and eat lunch at home after. However, they buy food during the morning from small snack shops that often serve low-quality food. As part of the BioCanteens initiative, Trikala – in collaboration with parents' associations, a university nutrition department, and organic farm – developed a transformation plan to renovate these snack shops to offer fresh and organic products.

- **Policy impact:**

In France, since the implementation of the program, the city of Mouans-Sartoux serves 1,000 self-produced local and organic meals every day to children across three schools. Meals are 100% organic and 70% sourced from local agriculture. 85% of the organic food served is sourced from the municipal farm. Thanks to this programme, Mouans-Sartoux has reduced the carbon impact of its residents by more than 20% in five years. It has reduced the consumption of processed industrial foods and meat

and doubled the consumption of organic and local products compared to the French average. It has also reduced food waste by around 80%, from approximately 150g to 30g per plate. The price of a 100% organic meal is fixed at 2.01 euros, while in France an industrial non-organic school meal costs between 1.50 and 2 euros on average.

Some lessons learned from this project were the necessity of an enabling context through an integrated sustainable territorial project, policy creativeness, adapting for the local context, acknowledging that some changes will happen in the long term (evolution of practices and behaviours). Although this program was very successful, some areas of improvement were highlighted for even stronger impact: empowering the kitchen staff to lead in the canteen project, finding new financing and securing the economic sustainability of the initiatives, and building synergies with higher education programs to transfer good practices.

The network also led to success stories in partner cities.

In Troyan, Bulgaria, success from the transfer process benefited from a strong involvement of the mayor, financial capacities to fund the project, suitable land owned by the city, an efficient existing canteens system, good mobilisation of stakeholders. In April 2021, the municipality had established one orchard expected to yield about 10 tonnes of apple a year and another expected to yield between 900 and 1,500 kg of plums a year. The greenhouses are used to grow lettuce, green onions, tomatoes, cucumbers, and peppers.

The initiative is expected to save money and preventing an increase in kindergarten fees. There are also plans to produce honey from municipal beehives and collect local herbs. The project also aims to involve disabled children and youth from a local day center in gardening activities.

[Small Bulgarian Town Sets Up Municipal Gardens to Grow Organic Produce for Kindergartens | Nieuwsbericht | Agroberichten Buitenland](#)

In Italy, the city of Rosignano Marittimo ensured its caterers increased their share of organic products from 60 to 80% and used local products such as olive oil, tomato, pasta, and bread.

In Portugal, the city of Torres Vedras managed to increase its overall share of organic produce distributed in school canteens to its 30% objective in 2022.

In Greece, COVID lockdown delayed progress and the transformation remained limited by entrenched cultural habits and administrative routines.

Key learnings from the BioCanteens in these transfer stories highlight that:

- Canteen schemes are part of a large and interconnected system of stakeholders. Providing healthy and sustainable food for children can be a valuable and consensual entry towards a wider range of transition issues.
- Despite their small-medium size, the purchase power of canteens can influence the local agricultural fabric.
- Educating children on sustainable and healthy food can shift the eating habits of their whole families, as well as their attitudes towards food waste.
- These programs can have wider indirect effects on cities' governance, pushing them to go beyond their official competencies by negotiating with external stakeholders and higher levels of governance.
- Generally, aiming high and trying to address broader goals as it was done in Mouans-Sartoux and Rosignano Marittimo led to greater outcomes than in the rest of the cities.
- It is possible to compensate higher costs of organic and local products by efficiently reducing food waste and increasing consumption of healthier and cheaper plant-based proteins.

2 – Slow Food's Earth Market Program in Slovakia

- **Case description:**

Slow Food is a global organisation that aims to prevent the disappearance of local food culture and traditions. As part of the organisation, Slow Food's Earth Market programme creates a commercial channel for local ecotypes, suited to limited demand, bringing together producers and artisans who can interact directly with customers, explaining who they are, how they make their products and how they set their prices. To be certified, Earth Markets must observe the following rules:

- They are intended exclusively for producers (no on-sell retailers),
- They must guarantee a varied and complete offer (with a minimum of 10 producers)
- They must be organised periodically at the same place and the same time.
- The packaging of the products must be minimal, easily decomposable, compostable, recyclable or reusable.

- Participants must describe their work in detail through a label or a sign on the stand
- Market producers must be selected based on a principle of proximity.
- Within the markets, there must be moments of education and awareness of Slow Food's philosophy.

In Slovakia, the pioneer application of this program happened in 2014 in Bratislava. In 2019, local farmer associations of the city of Bátovce reached out to the association for mentoring on how to create their own certified high-quality food market. Their objectives were ensuring food self-sufficiency for the local population, providing access to high-quality food and a niche market for local farmers to sell their products, and attracting visitors.

The local action group (LAG) engaged the municipality to find a suitable location, resulting in the use of a previously reconstructed farmhouse funded by the EU Rural Development Programme. Collaboration included public and private organisations and support from Slow Food Pressburg to replicate the Earth Market Code. Capacity building by the LAG ensured adherence to the code. The market opened in 2019, and by May 2022, it received full recognition from the Slow Food global network. The market features products directly from regional farmers, ensuring quality and origin.

- **Policy impact:**

The newly established market in Bátovce has provided around 30 local producers with a regular place to sell their products, enhancing their marketing and expanding their customer base. Satisfied customers have made additional orders, including special occasion orders for companies and schools. The market's permanent presence has strengthened ties among producers and customers, indirectly benefiting other local businesses by increasing visitor numbers and fostering entrepreneurial cooperation. The Batovce support this by promoting local attractions around the market to their customers. In May 2024, a new Slow Food Market was inaugurated in Slovakia, in the village of Kravania.

More broadly, in 2022, there were 88 active Earth Markets in the world in 25 countries involving 2100 producers.

- Project Website

trhbatovce.sk

[Slow Food - Good, Clean and Fair Food for All](#)

3 – Urban farming in Cuba

- **Case description:**

Before the 1990s, Cuban agriculture was mostly large-scale, monocultural, and chemically intensive. Following the fall of the USSR in 1989 – the source of more than 80M of Cuba's imports at the time – and the imposition of trade sanctions, Cuba entered a period of economic crisis. As resources dwindled and food became scarce, the government had to reorganise the country's agricultural system towards self-sufficiency (Koont, 2016). Citizens also took matters into their own hands, starting a Grow-Your-Own revolution.

In the 1990s, new institutions and policies allowed for a centrally directed organisation providing administrative, technical and material assistance to a decentralised network of small-scale agricultural production units in urban and semi-urban areas. Urban farms began popping up in unused lots of Havana and other cities, in home gardens, in lots of workplaces, and in larger units practising innovative technologies.

The Cuban Ministry of Agriculture has supported these initiatives. In 1993, the Third Agrarian Reform Law allowed for the transfer of the usufruct rights of 70% of Cuba's agricultural land to individuals, associations and cooperatives for farming. In 1994, an Urban Agriculture Department (UAD) was formed. Grassroots community organisers continue to receive government training and support, creating a healthy, diverse and accessible food supply for urban residents.

In 1997, Fidel Castro approved a model for profit sharing through the 'organopónicos', where farmworkers could augment their salaries with earnings from surplus produced. This made farming very popular in the country as salaries were fixed, and it was illegal to engage in most other forms of private entrepreneurship (Clouse, 2014). Hallmarks of Cuba's 'organopónico' system have been sustainable production, low levels of pesticide use, and other organic farming practices, such as crop rotation and soil management.

- **Policy impact:**

Farm output from Cuba's urban farms has been remarkably high. By 1995, food shortages had begun to lessen. Between 1994 and 2005, the production of vegetables and fresh herbs jumped from 4,000 tons to 4.2 million tons. This was due not only to a large increase in

cultivated area but also a considerable increase in yields per square meter – from 1.5 kg/sqm in 1994 to 25.8 in 2001 (Koont, 2009).

Moreover, not only did the provision increase, but the diversity of vegetables, livestock and plants also increased, improving the population's nutrition (Fernandez, 2017). With the transition to semi-organic farming in rural areas, the country became a leader in self-provisioning, and it has also innovated new agricultural infrastructures and is now an established world leader in sustainable food production (Clouse, 2014).

Havana experienced some specific issues, as it is the most densely populated city, and its agricultural areas are smaller and thus, the emphasis on using local production for local consumption led it to lag behind other provinces. Still, Havana managed to increase its production of vegetables at a very high pace (with a 38% annual increase between 1997 and 2005). This increase was also reflected in other types of crops such as banana, fruits, root crops, beans and rice. By 2002, in Havana alone, 12% of the city was cultivated by some 22,000 urban and peri-urban producers, and more than 50% of the perishables were produced within the city limits. Havana's urban agricultural workforce also grew accordingly from 9,000 in 1999 to 44,000 in 2006. In 2009, about 24% percent of this workforce was female on average (50% among highly technically qualified workers) (Koont, 2009).

Overall, the urban agriculture movement has generated more than 300,000 jobs and trained tens of thousands of farmers, technicians, and government officials (Fernandez, 2017).

We highlight that the restructuring of Cuba's agricultural systems was also greatly helped by consistent efforts of the government since the 1960s to improve human capital in the country through the implementation of universal primary and secondary education, an expanding tertiary education, the development of universities and the creation of specialised research centres. This transformation was also supported by strong social organisations, which supported the implementation of urban farming policies (Koont, 2016).

Another reason for this success is the new organisational structures that were created to connect small-scale production units with each other and with the central government. This allowed for a strong, coherent, central direction, guidance and policy combined with decentralised action in input provision, marketing, and production.

Policies adopted included the delivery of technical training, the supplying of botanical and agamic seeds, necessary tools, watering cans, incentive schemes, and growers' responsibility to supply social service institutions (Koont, 2016)

3 – Parisculteurs in Paris, France

- **Description of the project**

In 2016, the City of Paris launched the Parisculteurs program to facilitate and accelerate the installation of agricultural projects in Paris (Resilient Cities Network, 2023). This program follows the commitment made by the City of Paris in 2014 to green 100 hectares of Parisian walls or rooftops and to develop 30 hectares of urban agriculture by 2020 (Ecocites Logement). The idea is to find sites that can host farmers who want to establish their production in Paris and then, through public tenders, make them available for agricultural projects carried by third-party organizations (non-profits, companies, start-ups, etc.) (Resilient Cities Network, 2023). By endorsing the charter, these stakeholders agreed to actively support the implementation of urban farming initiatives on their properties, contribute to knowledge exchange, and help raise the visibility of the program (Ecocité Logement).

This approach allows for the establishment of a great variety of projects, both in terms of their aims (productive, recreational, participatory) and cultivation methods (greenhouse, open ground, underground, etc.) (Les Parisculteurs, n.d.).

- **Policy impact:**

The project underwent three rounds of evaluation: one focusing on the financing part, one output and environmental evaluation of the launched projects; and one operational report on program management.

According to this evaluation report, “today, the 100 acres Charter is signed by 74 major Parisian surface owners (2/3 of which are private companies), including: Enedis, RATP, Paris Habitat, the City of Saint-Denis, Carrefour group, the National Museum of Natural History, or the Galeries Lafayette Haussmann. [Regarding implementation,] around 300 rooftop structure and load capacity were inspected by the project team, 130 sites were submitted to the successive calls, 2000 candidates visited the sites, and 60 laureates are now being assisted in their installation” (Ecocité Logement).

Active projects include: 4 market gardening rooftops and a facade on Bastille Opera, an underground urban farm producing vegetables (100.000 kg/year) and mushrooms (30.000 kg/year), a 700m² saffron farm that regularly hosts pedagogical visits and culinary workshops. Paris now has more than 30 hectares of agricultural land within city limits.”

The evaluation reports identify the following factors that contributed to the success of the Parisculteurs initiative:

- a shared and explicit commitment of all stakeholders
- a comprehensive baseline review that ensures realistic goals
- a well-equipped and closely monitored project team.

Some areas for improvements noted were strengthening connections to initiatives in other areas (education, health) and further quantification of the outcomes of the initiatives (e.g., in terms of the number of jobs created)

Related policy entries

- Fostering the contributions of small farmers to regional production
- Producer platforms
- Increased space for community gardens

References

- [BIOCANTEENS: How one city went 100% organic at no extra cost - Organic Cities Network Europe \(organic-cities.eu\)](https://organic-cities.eu)
- [Inforegio - French BioCanteens seek to spread organic, local food from school canteens across Europe \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)
- [Biocanteens – Smart Rural Areas \(smartrural21.eu\)](https://smartrural21.eu)
- [BioCanteens lessons.pdf \(urbact.eu\)](https://urbact.eu)
- [A Food Market Code boosts job opportunities in Bátorovce, Slovakia | Rural Pact Community Platform \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)
- Clouse, C. (2014). *Farming Cuba: Urban agriculture from the ground up*. Chronicle Books.
- Enthoven, L., & Van den Broeck, G. (2021). Local food systems: Reviewing two decades of research. *Agricultural systems*, 193, 103226.
- Fernandez, M. (2017). Urban Agriculture in Cuba: 30 Years of policy and practice. *Urban Agriculture Magazine*, 33, 41-44.

- Kneafsey, M., Venn, L., Schmutz, U., Balázs, B., Trenchard, L., Eyden-Wood, T., ... & Blackett, M. (2013). Short food supply chains and local food systems in the EU. A state of play of their socio-economic characteristics. *JRC scientific and policy reports*, 123, 129.
- Koont, S. (2009). The urban agriculture of Havana. *Monthly Review*, 60(8), 44-63.
- Koont, S. (2016). *Sustainable urban agriculture in Cuba*. University Press of Florida.
- Urbact, & Biocanteens. (2021). *Copying neighbours: Lessons of Biocanteens transfer network*. Urbact.
- [Resilient Cities Network \(2023\). The Paris urban agriculture agenda – Parisculteurs.](#)
- [Les Parisculteurs \(n.d\). Parisculteurs in a nutshell.](#)
- Ecocites Logement. ISO/AFNOR 37101. Case study No.1 – Les Parisculteurs. French government.

Common trusts

A commons trust is a legal entity responsible for protecting a shared asset. Because it is common property, the commons are guarded against any claims by private individuals, businesses, government or other trusts. Trustees appointed by the stakeholders undertake legal and fiscal responsibility for the long-term preservation, use or production of the commons. Many types of commons can be managed with trusts (such as land, air, water, energy and housing) to benefit the public as a whole as well as future generations.

Case studies

There are many case study examples of common trusts. The following case studies highlight three specific instances where common trusts have been established for different objectives: 1) to support small agro-ecological farmers' access to land; 2) to preserve natural reserves; and 3) to ensure secure access to housing.

1 – Terre-en-vue in Wallonia and De Landgenoten in Belgium

- **Case description:**

Over the last 30 years, Belgium has lost around 60% of its farms, most of them being less than 50 hectares (Statbel, 2022). Over the same period, the average farm size has more

than doubled, concentrating land in large, environmentally unfriendly farms producing for big retailers. Increasing real estate pressure on agricultural land is causing speculation and high prices, hindering new farmers and intergenerational farm transfers (Terre-en-vue, 2023a).

Terre-en-vue in Wallonia and De Landgenoten in Flanders acquire land using citizen savings and then lease it to agro-ecological farmers under long-term, fair lease terms. These social enterprise cooperatives act as a tool for solidarity-based investment, enabling citizens and organisations to invest a portion of their savings by purchasing shares to support the acquisition of agricultural land.

The initiative aims to make land more accessible for agro-ecological farmers in Belgium, protect land from speculation through collective ownership, and support sustainable agriculture (Terre-en-vue, 2023b). It fosters solidarity among farmers, strengthens citizens' connection to their land, boosts rural economies through diverse and direct agricultural projects, and empowers citizens and farmers to have a say in their territories through popular education and land democracy.

- **Policy impact and evaluation:**

At the end of 2022, ten years after its creation, Terre-en-vue made 176 hectares available to 43 farms, which together cultivate more than 600 hectares. The organisation has 3,445 members, each holding an average of €2,100 in shares, amounting to a total contribution of over €7 million. The initiative continues to be very dynamic, with member contributions and hectares made available doubling in 2022 compared to the previous year (Terre-en-vue, 2022).

In 2022, Terre-en-vue also estimated its wider social impact. The study found that Terre-en-vue successfully created a strong community around concrete actions and ideas addressing complex issues like land access, food sovereignty, and environmental concerns. This sense of belonging and the coherence between actions and values enhance mobilisation among cooperators, supporters, and farmers and provide a sense of agency. Active participation in Terre-en-vue enhances understanding of systemic and political issues for advocating land regulation. Terre-en-vue's processes reduce farmers' mental stress, foster a sense of community support, and improve wellbeing and work conditions. Terre-en-vue also introduces farmers to new perspectives on land ownership, providing a sustainable solution for land management while preserving freedom and autonomy in their professional choices (SAW-B, 2022).

The Flemish counterpart of Terre-en-vue, De Landgenoten, made 47 hectares available to 14 farmers in 2022.

While these results are inspiring, Terre-en-vue notes that it cannot single-handedly solve land access and speculation issues, which require political regulation.

- **Link to external source:**
 - [Terre-en-vue - Faciliter l'accès à la terre pour une agriculture durable](#)
 - [Brengrond tot leven | De Landgenoten](#)

2 – Little Traverse Conservancy in the United States

- **Case description**

In the United States, land trusts have been popular since the 1980s to acquire ecologically and historically important lands that are too small to meet the standards for national parks and reserves. These land trusts can be established for various objectives such as conservation of biodiversity, providing a buffer habitat for larger protected areas or allowing for recreational opportunities.

The Little Traverse Conservancy (LTC) was founded in 1972 in Michigan as a private organisation that uses a combination of economic and social incentives to inspire people to preserve the land and scenic areas of Northern Michigan. Historically, its focus has been on the conservation of the aesthetics of the landscapes of the region for future generations, more than the preservation of the ecological importance of the natural areas.

The LTC uses various strategies to do this: conservation easements (voluntary, legally binding agreements between the landowner and the LTC that restrict development on a property to preserve its natural or historic values while allowing the landowner to retain ownership and potentially receive tax benefits), monetary and land donations, purchasing lands, community involvement, creating partnerships, media outreach, and developing education programmes. They organise community field trips and build trails in an effort to connect local communities to their natural environment.

- **Policy impact:**

LTC has preserved natural areas in five counties of Northern Michigan. It counts over 4400 members and over 300 volunteers (Little Traverse Conservancy, 2024). As of June 2023, 330 privately owned lands have been given permanent protection with conservation easements, 400 nature preserves have been established, and 38 working forest reserves

are open to the public with more than 160 kilometres of trails available (Little Traverse Conservancy, n.d.).

In total, the LTC land trust owns over 9200 hectares of land and has conserved over 9034 more hectares through easements (Land Trust Alliance, n.d.). The LTC has partnered with Michigan's state resource agency to acquire state parks, state forests, and state wildlife research areas.

One limitation of this project is that, due to the ecological preservation not being the first objective of the land trust, the ecological value of lands acquired by this land trust has for long not been quantified and thus the role they play in ecological conservation remains unknown. However, considering the LTC has avoided developments on these lands, we can safely assume that biodiversity conservation happened even if it was not quantified (Braddock & Heinen, 2017). Moreover, in 2024, the LTC launched a programme to identify, quantify and evaluate the habitat types, health and status of the lands they look after in cooperation with the US Fish and Wildlife Service. Based on the results, they will formulate response actions to maintain the sites and improve degraded areas.

The land trust has likely had a significant positive impact on biodiversity conservation, even though ecological preservation was not its primary objective. However, for improved environmental impact, lands acquired should be systematically monitored for conserving biodiversity, and conservation goals should be set (Braddock & Heinen, 2017). Moreover, as the trust becomes more established, it should develop refined criteria for land acquisition and protection.

- **Link to project website:**

[Northern Michigan Land Trust | Little Traverse Conservancy](#)

3 – Dudley Neighbors Inc. in the United States

- **Case description:**

Dudley Neighbors Inc. (DNI) is a community land trust formed in 1988 to serve the Roxbury/North Dorchester area of Boston, Massachusetts. Facing significant challenges such as vacant land, toxic waste dumping, and economic decline, the Dudley Street Neighborhood Initiative (DSNI) mobilised residents and community organisations to take control of their neighbourhood's development by establishing the DNI. DSNI was the first community-based nonprofit in the country granted eminent domain authority over land

within its boundaries, meaning that it can expropriate private property for public use, with payment of compensation. Thanks to this, the DSNI was allowed to acquire and manage land through its subsidiary, Dudley Neighbors Inc. Because DSNI had engaged in a community-led planning process and developed a plan aimed at protecting the interests of residents and businesses, it received support not present in many other eminent domain cases (Loyola University). The DNI is holding land in perpetuity for the benefit of current and future generations and focuses on building affordable housing, commercial spaces, greenhouses, and community facilities (Crabtree, Phibbs, Milligan & Blunden, 2012).

- **Policy impact:**

DSNI facilitated the construction of 207 homes between 1994 and 2008, including owner-occupied, rental, and cooperative housing. This significantly reduced the number of vacant lots and abandoned properties, transforming them into liveable spaces that support community stability.

The programme also strengthened social cohesion and the empowerment of local residents. By turning vacant lots into homes, the initiative helped create wealth within the community. This resilience was crucial in mitigating the effects of the subprime housing crisis, as the programme protected residents from predatory lending and foreclosure (Engelsman, Rowe, & Southern, 2018). Moreover, the initiative's success helped the community secure nearly \$10 million in funding from various sources and gain support from city and state officials. This capacity enabled DSNI to expand its activities, including involvement in local education and environmental initiatives.

The programme was so successful that one of the most undesirable neighbourhoods now faces increased interest from private developers. However, as the land trust continues to have the right to claim vacant land, the community control remains strong (Thaden, Pickett, & Network, 2019).

An evaluation study of Dudley Neighbors Inc highlighted several lessons that can be learned from the implementation of this project:

1. The Community Land Trust model can be adapted to fit the concerns and priorities of the participants, although it should always ensure broad representation and balanced shareholder interests.
2. Formulating a comprehensive housing and social programme in the redevelopment program can help to improve the safety and appearance of the land, combat criminal activity and provide various social services.

Related policy entries:

- Community gardens
- Encourage decentralised and distributed energy

References

- [Resident and Community Engagement in Community Land Trusts \(lincolnst.edu\)](#)
- Braddock, K. N., & Heinen, J. T. (2017). Conserving Nature through Land Trust Initiatives: A Case Study of the Little Traverse Conservancy, Northern Michigan, USA. *Natural Areas Journal*, 37(4), 549–555. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/90015619>
- Crabtree, L., Phibbs, P., Milligan, V., & Blunden, H. (2012). Principles and practices of an affordable housing community land trust model.
- [De Landgenoten. \(2023\). Infographic: koop landbouwgrond voor bioboeren.](#)
- Engelsman, U., Rowe, M., & Southern, A. (2018). Community Land Trusts, affordable housing and community organising in low-income neighbourhoods. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 18(1), 103-123.
- Land Trust Alliance. (n.d.). *Little Traverse Conservancy*. Accessed on 2024, July 29 from <https://landtrustalliance.org/land-trusts/explore/little-traverse-conservancy-mi>
- [Little Traverse Conservancy. \(2024\). Annual Report 2023.](#)
- Little Traverse Conservancy. (n.d.). *What we do*. Accessed on 2024, July 29 from <https://landtrust.org/what-we-do/>
- SAW-B. (2022). [Evaluation de l'impact social de "Terre-en-vue" : rapport final.](#)
- Statbel. (2022). *Chiffres clés de l'agriculture 2022*.
- [Terre-en-vue \(2022\). Rapport annuel 2022.](#)
- Terre-en-vue. (2023, April 21). *Enjeux*. Accessed on 2023, July 29 from <https://terre-en-vue.be/presentation/article/constats>
- Terre-en-vue. (2023b, Septembre 26). *La coopérative*. Accessed on 2023, July 29 from <https://terre-en-vue.be/presentation/la-cooperative/article/la-cooperative>

- Thaden, E., Pickett, T., & Network, G. S. (2019). Community Land Trusts: Combining Scale and Community Control to Advance Mixed-Income Neighborhoods.
- [Loyola University Chicago. \(n.d.\). Community-led use of eminent domain.](#)

Encourage decentralised and distributed energy

The transition from centralised energy grids to decentralised distributed energy systems has been accelerating as new technologies emerge and the pressure to achieve decarbonisation increases. Since large power stations relying on coal, oil, or gas exploitation are not profitable below a certain threshold of households supplied, decentralised generation systems and transitioning to local power generation have the potential to help complete decarbonisation of production systems.

Case studies

Several regions and countries have pioneered the adoption of decentralised energy systems, for example, in Germany (Noonan & Fitzpatrick, 2020). The following case studies demonstrate the potential of decentralised energy installations in both developed and developing countries. These examples are not exhaustive but provide insight into how different regions have approached the transition to more localised energy systems.

1 – The Isle of Eigg Heritage Trust in Scotland

- **Case description:**

Eigg is a small island in the Scottish Inner Hebrides with around 100 inhabitants and 10,000 annual visitors. The island has been owned and managed on behalf of the community by the Isle of Eigg Heritage Trust since 1997. It was the second community buyout in Scotland. The IEHT has now a number of subsidiary companies, such as Eigg Electric conducting.

The Eigg electricity generation system relies on hydro, wind and solar technologies, combined with battery storage and a distribution grid. To manage consumption, maximum usage limits were set for both households and businesses and all surplus power generation is redirected into heating community buildings. From the beginning, a major objective was to achieve total autonomy from the mainland by building expertise and training on the island and ensuring that the company would be able to operate and maintain its system independently.

- **Policy impact:**

Eigg Island's generation capacity increased over the years, and the island now generates virtually all (around 90 to 95%) of its electricity through renewable energy. This achievement, among others, has enabled the empowerment and retention of residents on the island, high-speed broadband access, economic development and job opportunities for residents. The island achieved a reversal from depopulation to repopulation, attracting new residents to the island. Moreover, through a strategy of cost minimisation in the design and operation of the system and through a flat rate tariff for energy sale, the cost of electricity for residents has decreased by two-thirds compared to what it was before Eigg Electric (Rae & Bradley, 2013). It is still more expensive than the cost on the mainland, but islanders accept it since it was even costlier before. Concerning CO2 emissions, although they do not disappear completely, they declined by 20% per household compared to the rest of the UK (Hernández, Monagas, de Lara & Corral, 2023). The project was awarded multiple awards.

The island is also home to other vibrant green projects such as the ECO-Eigg project for sustainable, low-impact businesses promoting green living, local food production, and circular economy initiatives and the Fuel for Life project, which consists of a long-term forest plan, a tree nursery and a wood fuel enterprise.

The successful implementation of this project has benefited from four years of meticulous development before implementation, combining three renewable sources that complement each other over the seasons to maximise available energy resources at all times, maintaining specialised expertise, securing funding, active involvement of residents and local government and exchanging best practices with other similar communities.

The Eigg experience shows that it is possible to live within ecological limits provided that the technical means for it are met (Hernández, Monagas, de Lara & Corral, 2023).

- **Link to external source:**

[Eigg Electric - The Isle of Eigg](#)

2 – Renewable Energy Communities in Italy

- **Case description:**

The European Directive on the promotion of energy from renewable sources establishes the possibility of creating "Renewable Energy Communities" (REC) for the production and

consumption of energy from renewable sources, encouraging the transition from a centralised to a decentralised energy system.

Placing citizens at the heart of the energy transition, RECs represent a model of virtuous socio-economic communities where citizens, businesses, and administrations become prosumers, actively integrated into a participatory and democratic process to support the energy transition. Article 2, paragraph 16, letter c) of the European Directive explicitly states that the main objective of renewable energy communities is to provide mental, economic, or social benefits to their shareholders or members, or to the local areas in which they operate, rather than financial profits.

An energy community can form when individual citizens, local authorities, small businesses, and cooperatives come together to become co-owners of "neighbourhood" renewable energy plants, exchanging energy for self-consumption. They also have the option to feed energy into the grid and receive incentives from the 'Energy Service Provider', allowing any excess energy produced to be sold back to the national energy provider.

The operation of an energy community involves various private and/or public entities, collectively forming a legal entity aimed at producing electricity through renewable sources such as photovoltaic installations. These installations can be shared (as in the case of a photovoltaic or wind installation available to the community) or individual (such as a photovoltaic installation on the roof of a house, business, public administration building, or condominium). The smart grid is an intelligent infrastructure connecting all actors of the energy community, which may also include advanced storage systems for electricity not immediately used.

- **Policy impact:**

Two case studies are presented: the first is the energy community of San Giovanni a Teduccio, in the eastern outskirts of Naples, which was one of the first experiments of Renewable Energy Communities (CER) in southern Italy, and the other is Turano Lodigiano, where the first renewable energy community in Lombardy was established.

The case of San Giovanni a Teduccio has become a model to be copied and replicated in other instances, primarily because it has demonstrated that bottom-up approaches function as social catalysts, stimulating the creation of new communities based on increased awareness of the social, economic, and environmental value of renewable energy use (Vito et al., 2023). In the case of Turano Lodigiano, the role of technologies has emerged not only as tools capable of quantifying environmental benefits but also as promoters of

sustainable behaviours, offering people the opportunity to better understand and manage the impact of their actions.

Among the factors that can determine the success of energy communities are certainly energy policies, which, in the form of subsidies and economic support, are rapidly expanding, especially thanks to increased availability of political support programs throughout Europe. The motivations that have driven the activation of energy communities vary, from energy supply reliability to self-sufficiency, and even combating energy poverty through the involvement of energy companies. But monetary benefits are not the only ones: environmental issues and the desire for energy independence are equally strong motivations.

3 – RevoluSolar in Brazil

- **Case description:**

Since 2012, the Brazilian government has allowed decentralised energy generation and, since 2015, the country has allowed a cooperative model for distributed and grid-connected energy. RevoluSolar is a Brazilian non-profit organisation, founded by a group of residents of Rio de Janeiro in 2015.

These solar cooperatives can be found in some of Rio de Janeiro's favelas. While a local distribution company already provided electricity in these locations, it is many times considered unreliable and expensive. Thus, inhabitants tend to rely on informal solutions. Through its cooperatives, RevoluSolar builds small microgrid systems to provide more reliable solar energy at a lower cost.

The power generated covers the needs of sponsored families and local institutions. It also provides environmental and ecological education for children and vocational training and employment for local populations.

- **Policy impact:**

The NGO estimates that all its installations combined generate over 200 MWh. By means of comparison, in 2022, electricity consumption in Brazil averaged 2.36 MWh per capita. This represents 16 tons of CO₂ avoided and over 34 000 euros in energy savings. In terms of social impacts, the NGO has trained 70 residents, provided education to over 100 children and provided direct positive impacts on over 2000 people.

Some projects supported by RevoluSolar include:

- Babilônia and Chapéu Mangueira Solar Energy Project: the first solar energy cooperative in a Brazilian favela, it installed solar panels on the roofs of a local resident association, a sports court and a school, forming a shared energy generation system benefiting 50 families. Expansion plans for 2024 aim to serve up to 100 families.
- Kurasí Tury project: in collaboration with two local indigenous associations, RevoluSolar built a solar system to power the school, the health post, the water pump and the community centre of the Terra Petra indigenous community. This program positively impacts 46 families. The installation has reduced energy costs, ensured a stable power supply during outages and supported local economic activities. Training sessions were organised with teachers and communicators, which led to the development of a booklet on solar energy from an indigenous perspective.
- Circo Solar project: through the installation of solar panels on the circus structure, it now generates 100% of the energy it consumes, saving on electricity bills and allowing for investment in other areas.
- 'O Sol Nasce para Todos' - Complexo de Favelas da Maré: this installation provides energy to a museum which is one of the largest favela complexes in Rio de Janeiro and which provides workshops on education, culture, communication and the environment. As part of the project, workshops were organised on conscious consumption, energy efficiency, and the climate crisis.
- **Link to external source:**

[Home - Revulusolar](#)

Relevant policy entries

The shift towards decentralised and distributed energy systems can be supported by various innovative policies. The Sustainable Prosperity database contains several policy entries aimed at promoting sustainable energy practices and involving local communities:

- Financially supporting social innovations for distributed energy resources
- Recommunalisation of energy supply
- Sharing revenues from renewable energy production with locals
- Common trusts

References

- [Brazil: electricity consumption per capita 2022 | Statista](#)
- Barrigh, J., & Gow, O. (2021). *Deploying distributed renewable energy to reduce the impacts of extreme heat on the urban poor*. Atlantic Council. Retrieved June 21, 2024, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep36628>
- Baigorrotegui, G., & Lowitzsch, J. (2019). Institutional aspects of consumer (co-) ownership in RE energy communities. *Energy Transition: Financing Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewables*, 663-701.
- Noonan E., & Fitzpatrick, E. (2020). *Will distributed energy resources (DERs) change how we get our energy?* European Parliamentary Research Service.
- Rae, C., & Bradley, F. (2013). The emergence of low carbon energy autonomy in isolated communities. *Journal of Technology Innovations in Renewable Energy*, 2(3), 205-221.
- Hernández, Y., Monagas, C., de Lara, D. R. M., & Corral, S. (2023). Are microgrids an opportunity to trigger changes in small insular territories toward more community-based lifestyles?. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 411, 137206.
- Vito, D., Pirelli, B., Bosone, M. (2023) Valutare le comunità energetiche: un nuovo modello sociale ed economico per attuare la transizione ecologica. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372189291_Le_Comunita_Energetiche_nuovi_modelli_socio-economici_e_organizzativi_della_collettivita_opportunita_e_rischi

Universal Basic Services

The term 'universal basic services' refers to the proposal to develop more and better collectively provided services that are free for all who need them, regardless of someone's income or status. Potential benefits of universal basic services include (Coote, Kasliwal & Percy, 2019):

- Equity: Providing public services reduces income inequalities as they meet basic needs on which low-income groups spend much of their income.

- **Efficiency:** by reducing transaction costs, avoiding duplication, and facilitating coordinated efforts across various services, UBS can deliver more effective and cost-efficient outcomes compared to market-driven approaches.
- **Solidarity:** UBS can promote shared responsibility, create opportunities for diverse social interactions and reduce inequalities.
- **Sustainability:** UBS can ensure long-term stability by focusing on prevention, helping stabilise economies and promoting environmentally friendly practices.

Case studies

There is a wide range of innovative policies aimed at enhancing the affordability and accessibility of public services around the world. Public services can cover many sectors, such as

- **Housing:** for example, Vienna (Austria) maintains affordable housing through municipal land ownership and subsidies.
- **Transport:** Luxembourg offers free public transportation across the whole country.
- **Healthcare:** the UK, France, Sweden (and more) offer universal free or heavily subsidised healthcare.
- **Education:** Public universities in Iceland, Slovenia, Argentina, Brazil, Finland (and more) are free or charge low tuition fees.

The following case studies offer a glimpse into effective UBS policies for which rigorous impact evaluation studies have been carried out.

1 – Universal Childcare in Norway

- **Case description:**

Norway has progressively scaled up its early childhood education and care (ECEC) programmes since the 1970s. Two pieces of legislation were particularly important for the development of universal childcare in the 2000s: the Kindergarten Act of 2005 and the Framework Plan for the Content and Tasks of Kindergartens. These two acts recognise children's right to participate and the principle of the best interest of the Child. Since 2009, early learning and childcare have been recognised as a legal right. Moreover, Norway has recognised explicitly the child as a rights holder since 2014 in its Constitution.

Norwegian parents with newborns receive up to 1-year paid parental leave. As a result, few children enter non-parental care prior to 9 months of age. After parental leave, parents have the choice of enrolling their children in publicly subsidised ECECs or receiving cash benefits for staying home with their children until the age of 3 (Zachrisson et al., 2023).

Childcare is not universally free, but the amount paid by parents depends on the number of children (30% reduction for a second child, 50% for three or more children) and their incomes. The maximum parent fee is established annually in the national budget and cannot exceed 6% of household income. Moreover, since 2015, families with annual household incomes below a certain threshold are entitled to 20 hours per week of free provision. Overall, childcare is publicly financed by national grants, parent fees and municipal funds.

The central government is responsible for funding and legal/regulatory aspects, but ownership is a public-private mix. Municipalities carry the main responsibility for delivering childcare services. All municipalities are mandated to provide the same services regardless of size and revenues. The Ministry requires municipalities to include kindergartens in their long-term planning and land use plans.

In summary, the universal childcare system in Norway was achieved through increasing the supply of places, lowering parents' fees and creating a right to a place for all children.

- **Policy impact:**

The expansion of the childcare offer in Norway has resulted in a substantial increase in full-time childcare enrolment, especially for younger age groups. Indeed, although the percentage of 1- to 5-year-olds enrolled in *barnebager* had already progressed from 2% in 1950 to 90% in 2000, at the time, 1 out of 3 children were still only attending part-time. Following the different legislative acts and increased service provision, full-time enrolment went up from 63.4% in 2000 to 98.5% in 2020 (Beach, J., 2022).

In 2022, more than 90% of Norwegian children aged 1 to 5 attended childcare full-time. This places Norway in the highest-ranking countries in the EU, especially for very young children ([Eurostat](#)). In 2022:

- 40.9% of children under 2 attended ECEC, compared to 10% on average in the EU. Norway ranks 1st in the EU.
- 94.7% of 2-years-old attended ECEC in 2022, compared to the 35.4% EU average. Norway ranks 2nd behind Iceland.

- 96.8% of 3-years-old attended ECEC in 2002, compared 88.8% on average in the EU. Norway ranks 3rd behind France and Belgium.

Parents thus choose very predominantly to send their children to kindergartens after their children turn 2, even though the government subsidises those who would prefer to educate their children at home until 3.

Early childhood education's potential benefits for children are numerous (depending on various factors such as quality of care): better brain development, promotion of language and school readiness. It can be a basis for acquiring foundational learned and reducing the gaps between socially advantaged and disadvantaged children (UNESCO).

Several studies focused on the Norwegian case have found that universal daycare help reduce inequalities between children for advantaged and disadvantaged background. First, while parents with higher education and income levels remain more likely to enrol their children into center-based care, this universal childcare policy reduced the utilization gap between the most and least educated families over time (Sibley et al, 2015). Second, attending childcare significantly reduced inequalities in children achievement across levels of parental education. For children in 5th grade with parent of low education, attending a center care significantly increased math and English test scores compared to those not attending. This effect decreases in magnitude as parents' education level increases (Zachrisson et al, 2023). Other studies have also observed this same effect when comparing income levels. Low-income children who were in ECEC at 18 months have language scores at 3 years that were, on average, higher than those for low-income children who did not attend ECEC. The estimate was null for high-income children and only approached significance for middle-income children (Dearing et al., 2018).

Other studies investigate whether this time spent in early childcare may increase children's risk of developing externalizing behaviour problems. Regardless of modelling strategy, they found very little evidence of this for attendance of 40 hours or less and only slightly elevated problems for the 4% of children in the sample who were in childcare for more than 40 hours (Zachrisson, Dearing, Lekhal & Toppelberg, 2013).

Lessons learned from various studies on the Norway case show that:

1. **The role of mothers on the demand side is crucial** for policy change through changing labour market patterns and demand for childcare (Ellingsæter & Gulbrandsen, 2007).

2. **As policies change, attitudes change,** and new norms emerge. For Norwegian mothers, institutional care for children over 2 is now viewed by a majority as the best form of care. This was observed among mothers of all socio-economic backgrounds and all parts of the country (Ellingsæter, Kitterød & Lyngstad, 2017).
3. **Segregation by socio-economic backgrounds can persist,** even with strict regulation as is the case in Norway, due to parental application behaviours (parents of similar socioeconomic background applying to similar centres), and private centre cherry-picking advantaged students (Drange & Telle, 2020).

2 – Affordable housing associations in the Netherlands

Although this example does not completely fit the definition of universal basic services due to its income eligibility criteria, it does provide informative inputs into the discussion of universal basic services in the context of housing. Indeed, this case study presents a large-scale housing services programme that is organised to meet social needs of the population and has achieved financial stability. However, this system has also faced criticisms for leaving behind lower-middle-income households who are not eligible but often cannot afford housing in the regular housing market.

Case description

The first housing associations (HAs) appeared in the Netherlands between 1850 and 1860 as cooperatives founded by well-off workers and employers, following an ideal of philanthropic capitalism. In 1901, the Housing Law marked an increasing state intervention by setting standards for housing quality and establishing a framework for government support to housing associations. Religious housing associations and local municipal housing associations started to appear. Following World War II, the government started to subsidise generously HAs to construct a large number of social rental dwellings. After the 1980s, government subsidies started to disappear as HAs achieved financial independence and broadened their activities towards other social projects, public purpose building and commercial real estate. However, with this movement of marketisation and neo-liberalisation of the HAs, accusations of fraud and mismanagement started to appear. In 2011, the central government took back control of HAs and in discussion with the European Commission, new housing allocation rules were established to target more socially disadvantaged populations (Joris, 2017).

Today, Dutch Housing Associations are private, nonprofit enterprises that manage around 75% of the rental homes in the Netherlands and 35% of the entire housing stock. HAs are required to lease 80% of their vacant units to low-income families and 10% to intermediate income families. Rents are determined through a regulated point system and are maintained below market levels. Rents depend on the market value of the property, the dwelling characteristics (such as size, facilities or energy efficiency). Rents can only increase at a set, predetermined rate each year (Sainz, 2023)

The fund model of HAs is sustained by rental income and proceeds from selective property sales, which are reinvested in new housing developments, renovations and neighbourhood regeneration projects. It does not rely on direct government subsidies but instead on structures that allow HAs to secure credit at very favourable rate (Sainz, 2023).

One of those structures, the Central Fund for Social Housing (CFV), is the primary financial regulator for HAs. It strictly supervises the activities, financial management and governance of the housing associations.

- **Policy impact:**

Housing associations provide good quality affordable housing by renting out 2.3 million dwellings. In 2014, around 85% of the lower-income group renting their accommodation benefited from a regulated rent below 700 euros. For the lower middle-income group and the middle middle-income group, this was around 50 and 30%, respectively (Schilder & Scherpenisse, 2018).

The Dutch model for affordable housing associations has been regarded as a successful approach to ensuring both social objectives and financial autonomy and stability.

However, in recent years, the housing supply in the Netherlands has not kept up with demographic trends, and the housing cost overburden rate reached 9.5% in 2023 (higher than the Eu average of 8.9%). Although rents in affordable housing remain capped, the increasing needs have left some parts of the population unable to access those houses. However, this issue is not specific to the social sector but to the whole housing market.

Nevertheless, this example presents some interesting findings for discussion on delivering universal basic services, namely:

- Achieving financial stability without relying on direct government subsidies is possible. The use of commercial practices to support social objectives can serve as an example of innovative financial strategies to support public goods.
- The importance of good governance and a robust regulatory framework to maintain the integrity of the system and ensure good service delivery is crucial, especially in cases where the risk of moral hazard is high.
- Stricter income limits for allocation can create a process of *residualization* (increasing concentration of lower income groups in a shrinking social rental sector) and leave behind those households with slightly higher income (Joris, 2017). This process also leads to increasing spatial segregation and perceptions of unfairness from some native Dutch citizens (Sainz, 2023). This highlights even more the advantages of a system that would truly be universal.
- The access to universal access to services is very much dependent on the quantity of supply of such services. One of the major issues of the housing market in the Netherlands is that the supply of residential buildings in the last decade has failed to follow the increased demand. For households eligible for social housing, this has led to increasing waiting times to access such housing. For low-income households ineligible for social housing, this has left them with hard-to-find and pricey options on the regular liberalised housing market (Geis, 2023).

References

- Dearing, E., Zachrisson, H.K., Mykletun, A., Toppelberg, C.O. (2018). Estimating the Consequences of Norway's National Scale-Up of Early Childhood Education and Care (Beginning in Infancy) for Early Language Skills. *AERA Open*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858418756598>
- Coote, A., Kasliwal, P., & Percy, A. (2019). Universal basic services: Theory and practice-a literature review.
- [Jane Beach \(2022\) More than spaces: Creating universal child care in Norway. Child Care Canada. ISBN 978-1-896051-77-2](#)
- Zachrisson, H. D., Dearing, E., Borgen, N. T., Sandsør, A. M. J., & Karoly, L. A. (2023). Universal Early Childhood Education and Care for Toddlers and Achievement Outcomes in Middle Childhood. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 17(2), 259–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2023.2187325>

- Ellingsæter, A. L., & Gulbrandsen, L. (2007). Closing the childcare gap: The interaction of childcare provision and mothers' agency in Norway. *Journal of social policy*, 36(4), 649-669.
- Ellingsæter, A. L., Kitterød, R. H., & Lyngstad, J. (2017). Universalising childcare, changing mothers' attitudes: Policy feedback in Norway. *Journal of Social Policy*, 46(1), 149-173.
- Drange, N., & Telle, K. (2020). Segregation in a universal child care system: Descriptive findings from Norway. *European Sociological Review*, 36(6), 886-901
- Geis, A. (2023). Housing supply in the Netherlands: the road to more affordable living.
- Joris, H. (2017). Reregulation and residualization in Dutch social housing: A critical evaluation of new policies. *Critical Housing Analysis*, 4(1), 31-39.
- Saiz, A. (2023). The global housing affordability crisis: Policy options and strategies. *MIT Center for Real Estate Research Paper*, (23/01).
- Schilder, F., & Scherpenisse, R. (2018). *Policy and practice: affordable housing in the Netherlands*. The Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.
- Zachrisson, H. D., Dearing, E., Lekhal, R., & Toppelberg, C. O. (2013). Little evidence that time in childcare causes externalizing problems during early childhood in Norway. *Child development*, 84(4), 1152-1170.
- UNESCO. (2024). Global Report on Early Childhood Care and Education. The right to a strong foundation. [Global-report-on-early-childhoodcare-and-education-2024-1.pdf](#)
- Sibley, E., Dearing, E., Toppelberg, C.O. et al. Do increased availability and reduced cost of early childhood care and education narrow social inequality gaps in utilization? Evidence from Norway. *ICEP* 9, 1 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40723-014-0004-5>

Encouraging regenerative and distributive businesses

Policy shapes the kinds of businesses that populate our economies. Policies that encourage regenerative and distributive businesses are fundamental to help unlock the potential of

businesses in delivering social and ecological wellbeing. Policies targeted at fostering such enterprises can help to populate economies with resilient businesses that are committed to their communities and driven to achieve social and ecological goals.

In this context:

- 'regenerative' means that a business aims to work with and within the cycles of the living world.
- 'distributive' means that the business shares the value it creates with all who co-created it.

Case studies

Several countries actively encourage regenerative and distributive businesses. The Doughnut Economics Action Lab paper on Public Policies to foster regenerative businesses (DEAL, 2023) has compiled policy options and references to case studies for each of these policy approaches:

Development funds to support regenerative such enterprises

- Italy has a long-standing fund to support cooperatives, partly funded by a requirement that 3 percent of profits of all Italian cooperatives go to this fund.
- In France, Italy, Quebec (Canada) and Spain, cooperatives are required to allocate some of their surplus for the long-term collective benefit of all members, including future members. These allocations are not taxed and support the long-term resilience of these enterprises and promote a long-term focus.

Allow use of publicly owned premises

- In the Western Cape in South Africa, the government's provision of buildings to local cooperatives and social enterprises played a pivotal role in the success of those enterprises.

Create place-based hubs of support

- In cities around the world, projects and policies are supporting Impact Hubs, start-up hubs and broader business support hubs that deliberately focus on supporting regenerative and distributive businesses. One example is the London hub supporting

democratic businesses like co-operatives, mutuals, social enterprises, employee-owned, municipally-owned and community-owned businesses.

Target assistance for emerging industries

For emerging industries such as renewable energy, targeted assistance can ensure it has regenerative and distributive ownership as a core part of it. For example, the European Union has a package of policies and **directives** that together ease the way for community-owned renewable energy and provide technical and other assistance to support such community-owned enterprises and projects to emerge.

Exempt conversions from taxes

- In the US, a business sold fully to its employees (through employee share ownership plans) can be fully exempt from federal and most state income taxes. In addition, in Maryland, New York and Wisconsin there is an exemption from state capital gains tax if the majority of a business is sold to an employee ownership trust.
- The UK also has substantial tax exemptions applied to employees and shareholders where the business is converted into employee ownership.

Assist conversions of businesses

- Cities across the US have been providing funding for employee-ownership, including Santa Clara and Berkeley (California); Madison (Wisconsin); Austin (Texas); and Baltimore (Maryland).
- This has also happened at the national level in the US. Support often includes resources and information, technical assistance that supports retiring business owners to sell their businesses to workers, and training for members of new worker owners.

Require that employees have an option to invest in such enterprises

- In France, the law requires that employee savings schemes provide employees with the option to invest in 'solidarity-based enterprises'. This can eventually transform entire companies into employee ownership.

Support representation of workers on boards

- In Germany, codetermination provides workers the opportunity to actively participate in shaping decisions that impact their working environment. This extends to worker representatives sitting on company boards.

Provide constitutional recognition

- In the constitutions of Bolivia, Italy, Philippines, Taiwan and Yemen, the importance of cooperatives is explicitly recognised, often as a way of achieving objectives such as economic development, equity and social justice.

Pass common regional legislation

- Across 17 Central and Western African countries, a common legislation was passed in 2011 that promoted community-owned enterprises.
- In the United States, the Limited Cooperative Association Act is a model law for states that enables flexible co-op incorporation.

Create diverse legal forms for different contexts

- A range of legal forms are emerging that allow enterprises to shape their deep design in line with their needs and challenges. Alongside the diverse models of non-profit and cooperative legal forms around the world that allow for economic activity, there are other emerging models:
- The UK has created the Community Interest Company, the US has created the Low-Profit Limited Liability Company. California (US) created the Social Purpose Corporation, British Columbia (Canada) created the Community Contribution Company and Germany's ruling coalition are creating a new legal form for steward owned companies.
- In addition to legal forms, a range of countries have ways of recognising an enterprise as a public benefit corporation (e.g. Italy, Slovenia), a social enterprise (e.g. Thailand), social and solidarity company enterprise (e.g. France) or other regenerative community ownership enterprises in order to identify them for policy support. This can be a status that is acquired for enterprises that take any kind of legal form but demonstrate they are designed to prioritise public and social benefit

Ensure regenerative community ownership is not disadvantaged

- A range of tax exemptions and support packages targeting businesses in the US have often been unavailable to cooperatives and other alternative enterprise models. Recently, the loan guarantee programmes targeting businesses run by various US federal agencies were revised so they can support the conversion of businesses into

employee-ownership. Similarly, some tax codes were revised to ensure alternative enterprise models were not actively disadvantaged.

Actively shape public procurement

- Korea's Social Enterprise Promotion Act requires that public institutions both promote preferential purchase of goods or services produced by social enterprises and have a specific plan to achieve this.
- Across the world, including in Brazil, the UK, Luxembourg, South Africa and Greece, governments are developing policies to actively procure from social economy enterprises. Again, the goal might be to ensure that eventually all public procurement should go to regenerative enterprises.

Join forces with local anchor institutions

- The concept of Community Wealth Building, based on pioneering cities like Cleveland, Ohio, has been deployed in Preston, UK. The approach includes the local government joining forces with other organisations like universities and colleges in the area to use their collective buying power to support regenerative community ownership and other models beneficial for local development. For instance, the Preston Procurement Practitioners Group was formed to help procurement officials collaborate in preferencing community enterprises in their procurement.

Ensure appropriate tax treatment

- Tax codes are often designed with investors, not communities, in mind. In Belgium, a dedicated tax code was created for cooperatives, including clarifications on payments to members, social security for workers and a reduced corporate tax rate.
- The Portuguese Framework Law on the Social Economy and the Brazilian Constitution also have a similar focus on creating a more favourable fiscal status for cooperatives and social economy enterprises.

Encourage a regenerative investment ecosystem

- Luxembourg created a Societal Impact Company as a category of enterprise, where investments into 'impact shares' (drawing no dividends, only return of capital) are given a range of tax breaks. Enterprises exclusively with impact shares are given additional tax advantages, including exemptions from corporate income tax, communal business tax and wealth tax.

- Thailand has also created corporate income tax exemptions for investment into recognised social enterprises.

Policy impact:

A wide range of evaluation studies have shown the value of regenerative and distributive business models for various outcomes such as job security, productivity, workplace conflict, and retirement savings. For example:

In relation to employee ownership:

- Biasi et al. (2017) found that employee-owned companies, particularly those with Employee Stock Ownership Plans (ESOPs), tend to have higher productivity, better survival rates during economic downturns, and greater employee engagement compared to non-employee-owned firms. Employee ownership was associated with a 4-5% increase in productivity, higher job satisfaction, and lower turnover rates. They also found that employee ownership significantly enhances retirement savings.
- A meta-analysis on the relationship between employee ownership and firm performance by O'Boyle et al. (2016) of 102 samples representing 56,984 firms found a positive and statistically significant relation to firm performance. The effect is generally positive for studies with different sampling designs (samples assessing change in performance pre-employee–post-employee ownership adoption or samples on firms with employee ownership), different performance operationalisations (efficiency or growth) and firm type (publicly held or privately held).
- Rosen, Case, and Staubus (2005) found that employee ownership reduces workplace conflict by aligning the interests of employees and management, fostering a more cooperative and less adversarial work environment.
- Mygind & Poulsen (2021) provide an overview of existing empirical evidence on employee ownership. They find that the benefits include greater employee identification with the firm and increased productivity, reinforced by increased participation. Employee-owned firms have a more equal distribution of wages and more stable employment, and they have greater mutual control between employees and fewer middle managers. The motivation effects may be smaller for large firms,

and a lack of capital may lead to lower levels of investments and capital per employee.

In relation to social enterprises:

- [The State of Social Enterprise: A Review of Global Data 2013–2023](#) indicates that there are approximately 10 million social enterprises across the world, generating around \$2 trillion in revenue each year and creating nearly 200 million jobs. Social enterprises play an important role in bridging the gender gap, with one in two social enterprises worldwide led by women, compared to one in five for conventional enterprises. Social enterprises operate in diverse sectors such as healthcare, education, renewable energy, agriculture and more and play a pivotal role in advancing the SDGs.
- Research by The British Council (2024) similarly finds that social enterprises are much more likely to be led by women and that social enterprise leaders also tend to be young. In most countries, leaders tended to be between 25 and 44 years old.
- [The British Council research](#) further shows how social enterprises are often significant employers, in proportion to their size. For countries in Sub-Saharan Africa for which there is data, registered micro, small and medium-sized enterprises employ an average of two people, while social enterprises employ an average of 21. Survey data shows that this is likely a result of their explicit missions to create jobs, with only 27 per cent of profit-first businesses actively seeking to create jobs, compared to 78 per cent of social enterprises.
- According to data by the Schwab Foundation for Social Entrepreneurship tracking a global community of over 470 leading social entrepreneurs, these enterprises alone have already directly impacted more than 891 million lives over the past 25 years. <https://www.schwabfound.org/what-is-the-impact/>
- The Social Enterprise UK (SEUK) [State of Social Enterprise Survey 2023](#) found that Social enterprises in the UK's most deprived communities reinvested more than £270m profit – equivalent to more than a fifth of the amount invested through Phase Two of the Government's Levelling Up Fund.
- The European Commission 2020 evaluation of the Social Business Initiative, which included measures such as funding, regulatory support, and capacity-building programs, found that these policies had a positive impact on the development of

social enterprises across Europe. The initiative contributed to increased visibility, better access to finance, and improved regulatory frameworks for social enterprises. The initiative helped increase the number of social enterprises, enhance their financial sustainability, and boost their capacity to address social challenges.

Related policy entries

- Tax relief and financial support instruments for cooperative platform companies
- Tax benefits for employee cooperatives
- Reduction of bureaucratic barriers and accounting requirements for cooperatives
- Creation of a separate legal form for democratic / participative companies
- Tax benefits for employee cooperatives
- See also: Support sustainable social innovation (new entry)

References

- Blasi, J., Freeman, R., Kruse, D., et al. (2017). "Having a Stake: Evidence and Implications for Broad-based Employee Stock Ownership and Profit Sharing.
- DEAL (2023), Regenerative Business Rising tool, Doughnut Economics Action Lab, <https://doughnuteconomics.org/tools/public-policies-to-foster-regenerative-businesses>
- European Commission (2020). Impact of the European Commission's Social Business Initiative (SBI) and its Follow-up Actions, <file:///Users/margreetfrieling/Downloads/KE-01-20-767-EN-N.pdf>"
- Mygind, N., & Poulsen, T. (2021). Employee Ownership: Pros and Cons - A Review. Journal of Participation and Employee Ownership, 4(2), 136-173. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPEO-08-2021-0003> Social enterprises The World Economic Forum
- O'Boyle, E., Patel, P.C., Gonzalez-Mulé, E. (2016). Employee ownership and firm performance: a meta-analysis. Human Resource Management Journal, 26 (4), DOI: 10.1111/1748-8583.12115
- Rosen, C., Case, J., & Staubus, M. (2005). Equity: Why Employee Ownership Is Good for Business. Harvard Business Review Press.

- The British Council, 2022, More in common. The global state of social enterprise, https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/more_in_common_global_state_of_social_enterprise.pdf

Granting Rights to Nature

Rights of Nature (RoN) refers to the legal recognition and protection of the inherent rights of natural entities and ecosystems, allowing them to exist, thrive, and evolve (Cormac, 2011). Rights of Nature enables the legal defence of the environment in court – not only for the benefit of people, but for the sake of nature itself.

Case studies

Several countries have granted Rights to Nature, recognising ecosystems as legal entities with specific rights. Examples include:

- **Ecuador:** Ecuador was the first country to include Rights of Nature in its constitution in 2008. This legal framework allows nature to be a plaintiff in court, represented by people or organisations on its behalf. The inclusion aims to balance human activities with the ecological rights of natural systems.
- **Bolivia:** Bolivia introduced the "Law of the Rights of Mother Earth" in 2010. This law grants nature the right to exist and regenerate its life cycles. It reflects the indigenous worldview of Pachamama (Mother Earth) and aims to integrate indigenous values into national policy.
- **New Zealand:** In 2014, New Zealand granted legal personhood to the Whanganui River, recognising it as a living entity with legal rights. The law was part of a settlement between the government and a Māori iwi (tribe) who view the river as its ancestor. Similarly, in 2017, the Te Urewera forest was also granted legal personhood. These measures have strengthened indigenous governance and environmental stewardship, setting a precedent for recognising natural entities in law.
- **India:** Indian courts have recognised the Ganges and Yamuna rivers as living entities with legal rights in a bid to protect them from pollution and environmental harm. This judicial recognition draws from the doctrine of Parens Patriae, where the state acts as a guardian for entities unable to represent themselves.

- **Colombia:** The Colombian Constitutional Court recognised the Atrato River as a legal person in 2016, granting it rights to protection, conservation, and restoration. This decision has led to various initiatives to protect the river's health and ecosystem, involving local communities and authorities in enforcement efforts.
- **Panama:** In 2022, Panama passed a law granting nature the right to exist, persist, and regenerate. The law requires all government actions to favour the protection of nature, reflecting a broader ecocentric approach in policymaking.
- **Uganda:** The Uganda 2019 National Environment Act includes provisions that recognise the Rights of Nature. The 2019 Act explicitly recognises the right of nature to exist, persist, maintain, and regenerate its vital cycles. It introduces the concept of ecological integrity and emphasises the need to protect natural resources for the benefit of present and future generations.
- **United States:** In 2019, the Lake Erie Bill of Rights was passed by the residents of Toledo, Ohio, recognising the lake's right to "exist, flourish, and naturally evolve."

Policy impact

Rights of Nature laws have facilitated a paradigm shift in environmental law, emphasising ecological integrity and sustainable management. One of the strengths of a legal approach is that it is a long-term measure, as future administrations must amend or repeal the legislation if they wish to end it, requiring further debate, discussion and consensus forming. Rights of Nature laws can serve as an important accountability and commitment device by delineating the 'safe space' for governments to work within.

While the legal frameworks are progressive, enforcement and practical outcomes have, however, been mixed.

- The Vilcabamba River was the first successful case of the Rights of Nature implementation in **Ecuador**, where the Loja Provincial Court recognised the rights of the Vilcabamba river in a lawsuit against the construction of the Los Encuentros hydroelectric project and ordered significant restoration of the river's capacity to flow and support life.
- In **Colombia**, Indigenous and Afro-Colombian communities filed a lawsuit due to pollution from illegal mining affecting the Atrato River. The Constitutional Court of Colombia recognised the Atrato River as a legal entity with rights to protection,

conservation, maintenance, and restoration. The ruling mandated the government to undertake river restoration and granted local communities a role in managing and protecting the river.

- In **India**, a public interest litigation was filed to address severe pollution and ecological degradation of the Ganges and Yamuna Rivers. The Uttarakhand High Court declared these rivers as legal entities with the rights to be protected and preserved. The ruling aimed to improve the rivers' conditions, though it faced implementation challenges and was later overturned by the Supreme Court of India on jurisdictional grounds
- In the case of **Bolivia**, the original Rights of Nature Law in Bolivia, which was drafted as part of a nine-month negotiation process between the government and the “Unity Pact,” a coalition of Bolivian Indigenous organisations, had an ecocentric orientation and established that whenever there was a conflict of interests, the protection of Mother Earth should prevail. Instead, the law that was ultimately approved by the Bolivian government did not include this ‘conflict of interest’ clause, as it was felt to go against economic development interests, in the country where poverty is widespread and natural-resource extraction activities are seen as the fastest way to bring in enough economic resources. The adoption of the final law was opposed by the members of the “Unity Pact,” who felt alienated and withdrew from the legislative process, on the basis of there being irreconcilable differences regarding the content of the draft laws and those that were finally approved. Bolivian attorney, Lorna Muñoz (2023) describes that an ongoing issue in Bolivia has been the discrepancy between the Rights of Nature and other constitutional provisions, laws and regulations that favour economic interests, create language ambiguity and cause enforceability problems.

References

- Cullinan, C. (2011) *Wild Law: A Manifesto for Earth Justice*. Chelsea Green Publishing.
- Muñoz, L. (2023). Bolivia's Mother Earth Laws. Is the Ecocentric Legislation Misleading? *ReVista*. Harvard Review of Latin America, <https://revista.drclas.harvard.edu/bolivias-mother-earth-laws-is-the-ecocentric-legislation->

The creation of LabCDMX helped create a movement of urban laboratories that spread through South America, including in Buenos Aires, Laboratorio de Gobierno in Chile (the first Laboratory at the federal level), Lab. Rio in Rio de Janeiro, Lab Quito in Ecuador, Santa Lab in the Santa Fe Region in Argentina, Lab Capital in Bogotá and Montevideo Lab in Uruguay.

- In **Bologna**, the [Civic Imagination Office](#), created by the city municipality, promotes listening, collaboration, participation, and co-production related to projects and policies in the city, its neighbourhoods, and the entire metropolitan area. The specific focus is on the care and regeneration of urban common goods.

Bologna's Civic Imagination Office comprises a diverse team of experts in architecture, urban planning, sociology, and policy. This multidisciplinary team is dedicated to designing and supporting participation, collaboration, and co-planning activities initiated by the local government. A key element of this initiative is the establishment of 'proximity agents', with one assigned to each of the six neighbourhoods in Bologna. These agents work in coordination with the Networks and Community Work Offices, organising meetings, workshops, and focus groups.

The Civic Imagination Office's activities span both physical transformations, such as the use of buildings or projects in public spaces, as well as addressing issues of citizen concern, including mobility, air quality, and the management of public spaces. The focus is not only on mutual listening and creating shared understandings, but also on achieving real forms of co-production of decisions regarding public policies, involving both the local government and citizens.

- [Seoul \(South Korea\)](#), is a global leader in social innovation. The development of social innovation in Seoul has been closely linked to the idea of democracy and civic empowerment in South Korea. South Korea remained quite a traditional, authoritarian and patriarchal society with not much more than a generation since the end of the military dictatorship. Social innovation was a narrative used to redefine the relationship between the state and its citizens, towards more collaborative ways of working.

Policy impact:

As the field of social innovation is highly diverse and characterised by a wide range of social innovation initiatives in many different places around the world, evaluations tend to happen at the project/initiative level, and overall evaluations of social innovation as an overarching strategy are rare. However, the value of social innovation is widely recognised. For example:

- In April 2023, the UN General Assembly adopted the first resolution on [Promoting the Social and Solidarity Economy for Sustainable Development](#), on the basis that it advances all 17 of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. The resolution calls on governments worldwide to implement policies supporting social enterprises, cooperatives and social innovation.
- International bodies, including the EU, the African Union, the International Labour Organization and the OECD, have all adopted their own social economy action plans and recommendations.
- The book *The Impact of Societal and Social Innovation. A Case-Based Approach* (Yeh-Yun Lin & Chen, 2016) shows how social innovation efforts can benefit the underprivileged and society as a whole.

References

- Yeh-Yun Lin, C. & Chen, J. (2016). *The Impact of Societal and Social Innovation. A Case-Based Approach*, Singapore: Springer, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-1766-7>

Wellbeing budgets

Wellbeing budgets refer to the use of wellbeing metrics and frameworks to inform government budget spending. Instead of focusing on a relatively narrow set of economic indicators (e.g., economic growth, unemployment and inflation), wellbeing budgets assess the value of budget proposals against a more holistic set of wellbeing outcomes or goals.

By assessing budget proposals against their impact on wellbeing outcomes, wellbeing budgets encourage government agencies to think broadly in terms of policy impacts and to identify opportunities whereby actions in one policy area can create positive feedback loops that support the objectives in other policy domains. At the same time, a wellbeing lens

can help anticipate and mitigate risks where well-intended actions in one domain may trigger problems in other domains.

Wellbeing budgets have the potential to bring together efforts that apply specific lenses to budget allocation, such as a ‘gender’ or an ‘environmental’ lens, by looking at budget allocation through a multidimensional lens that incorporates each of these perspectives and acknowledges the interdependencies between achieving goals in each of these domains.

Case studies

Several governments at both national and regional levels have worked with wellbeing budgets, including the governments of:

- **New Zealand.** New Zealand introduced its first Wellbeing Budget in 2019, which was continued till 2023. The New Zealand Treasury used analysis of wellbeing data – based on both the [Living Standards Framework](#) and [He Ara Waiora](#) (the Māori wellbeing framework) - combined with advice from sector experts and the Government’s Chief Science Advisors, to identify a ‘longlist’ of approximately 10 to 15 wellbeing priority areas, which was then narrowed down by Ministers and Cabinet to 5 overall budget priorities: supporting a just transition to a climate-resilient, sustainable, and low-emissions economy; improving physical and mental health outcomes; shaping the future of work; lifting wellbeing outcomes for Māori and Pacific Peoples; and improving child wellbeing.

Between 2019 and 2023, the Budget Policy Statement started with a Wellbeing Outlook that outlined the state of wellbeing in New Zealand and described the wellbeing priorities for budget spending. The requirement for the New Zealand Government to report annually on its wellbeing objectives in the Budget has been anchored in the Public Finance (Wellbeing) Amendment Act 2020. The Public Finance (Wellbeing) Amendment Act 2020 also requires the Treasury to produce a Wellbeing Report, at least once every four years. Using indicators, the Wellbeing Report must describe the state of wellbeing in New Zealand, how wellbeing has changed over time, as well as its sustainability and any risks to it. The Treasury’s first [Wellbeing Report](#) was produced in 2022.

Following the release of the Budget Policy Statement, Ministries were invited to submit funding requests for policy proposals that are aligned with the identified government wellbeing priorities. In their proposals, ministries were required to provide

evidence of how their funding request supports wellbeing and to present expected wellbeing impacts, building on a cost-benefit analysis model called [CBAX](#) (including an optional monetary evaluation component) that was specifically aligned with a wellbeing approach (Jensen & Thompson, 2020).

Official website: www.treasury.govt.nz/

- **Bhutan.** The Bhutanese king, Jigme Singye Wnagchuck declared already in 1972, that the pursuit of happiness was more important for the country than the pursuit of wealth. The government's focus on happiness is anchored in the country's Constitution, stating that "The State shall strive to promote those conditions that will enable the pursuit of Gross National Happiness" (Article 9 of the 2008 Constitution). Over the past decades, Bhutan has been developing and using its own series of policy instruments that aim to put wellbeing at the forefront of public policy and planning, centred around its Gross National Happiness (GNH) framework.

The GNH framework is based on four pillars: 1) sustainable and equitable socio-economic development; 2) environmental conservation; 3) preservation and promotion of culture; and 4) good governance. These pillars are reflected in nine wellbeing outcome domains: psychological wellbeing, health, time use, education, cultural diversity and resilience, good governance, community vitality, ecological diversity and resilience, and living standards. In turn, progress for each of these 9 domains is informed by a set of approximately 30 indicators. A threshold is set for each indicator, which marks the level at which a person is deemed to have sufficiency of that particular outcome.

Beyond its use as a monitoring framework, GNH is also used as a framework for policy development and resource allocation. To help allocate resources, the GNH indicators show which wellbeing domains, as well as which regions and groups, are lagging behind others and are therefore in greater need of policy attention. The GHN Commission (a government planning body) further uses the GNH policy-screening tool to provide a systematic appraisal of the potential effects of proposed projects on the nine domains. A policy that fails to receive a sufficiently high score is not necessarily rejected, but is sent back to the proponent agency, outlining why it fell short, along with ways to improve it.

Official websites:

- www.gnhcentrebhutan.org/

- <https://ophi.org.uk/gross-national-happiness>
- **Iceland.** In 2019, Iceland introduced a framework of 39 [wellbeing indicators](#), based on a broad consultation process. The framework led to the identification of [six societal wellbeing priorities](#) that serve as the basis for the development of the government's five-year fiscal strategy and annual budget. The six priorities focus on improving mental health outcomes, providing secure housing, better work-life balance, zero carbon emissions, innovation growth, and better communication with the public. Budget allocation has shifted towards the achievement of these goals. Today, the six priorities steer 30 of the government's 35 policy areas. Following the use of wellbeing evidence in government priority setting, further work is underway to improve the way in which the wellbeing impact of policy proposals can be assessed.

Official website:

- www.government.is/topics/sustainable-iceland/well-being/what-is-a-well-being-economy/
- **Canada.** The Canadian Quality of Life framework aims to measure what matters most to Canadians, to help drive evidence-based budgeting and decision-making. The Canadian approach builds on its longstanding experience in the measurement of wellbeing as well as several existing tools and processes that were in place to ensure government decision-making and budgeting consider a broader range of data and evidence. For example, in 2018, the Gender Budgeting Act enshrined the Canadian Government's commitment to budget decision-making that considers the impacts of policy on diverse populations in Canadian society. This includes the publication of a '[Gender Based Plus](#)' analysis (GBA+) for all budget proposals. GBA+ is an analytical tool to systematically consider the potential implications of policies, programmes or initiatives on diverse groups, based on gender, but also age, income distribution, ethnicity, mental or physical ability, region, sector and other relevant factors.

Following the development of the Canadian Quality of Life Framework, the Department of Finance worked to develop a standardised approach for assessing policy and budget proposals across the multiple Quality of Life domains. To do so, the Budget Impacts Report was expanded from the existing Gender Based Plus analysis to also assess each budget proposal against its impact on Quality of Life. Using a standardised template, departments

were asked to describe: quality of life impacts, who is impacted, as well as sustainability and resilience impacts. This process was used to encourage budget proposals that would have the greatest wellbeing impacts, for the widest range of wellbeing domains, for the most vulnerable groups, now and in the long-term. A high-level overview of the expected Quality of Life impacts of budget proposals is made publicly available, alongside the Gender Based Plus analysis, in the [Budget Impacts Report](#).

References

- www160.statcan.gc.ca/about-afropos-eng.htm
- **Ireland.** In the *2020 Programme for Government – Our Shared Future*, the Irish Government has set out a commitment to utilising a wellbeing perspective to inform budgetary priorities as a complement to existing economic measurement tools. This is part of a wider commitment to develop a set of wellbeing indices to create a well-rounded, holistic view of how Irish society is faring and to utilise this approach in a systematic way across government policymaking.

Ireland's [Wellbeing Framework](#) was launched in July 2021. The Framework consists of eleven dimensions which constitute the different aspects of wellbeing: Environment, Climate and Biodiversity; Safety and Security; Housing and the Built Environment; Subjective Well-being; Knowledge, Skills and Innovation; Mental and Physical Health; Connections, Community and Participation; Work and Job Quality; Civic Engagement, Trust and Cultural Expression; Time Use; and Income and Wealth.

In 2022, the Framework and analysis of the accompanying dashboard were included in the Budgetary process through various means, including as a theme at the National Economic Dialogue (an annual stakeholder engagement event for public consultation and discussion on the Budget), featuring in the [Summer Economic Statement](#), as well as a new publication entitled '[Budget 2023: Beyond GDP – Quality of Life Assessment](#)'. The Irish government intends for this to be an [ongoing](#) and evolving annual contribution to the Budget process, which will support a broader discussion of the impacts of Budgetary decisions.

Still in 2022, a pilot “budget tagging” exercise was undertaken in Ireland as part of a project funded by the European Union's Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP) and supported by experts from the OECD. The exercise required participating Departments (including the Departments of Transport, Housing, Local Government & Heritage, and Tourism) to map their expenditure with reference to the Irish Well-being Framework,

alongside existing Equality Budgeting and Green Budgeting methods. The participating Departments reported that they found the tagging exercise to be a useful tool to better consider outcomes of their policies with respect to wellbeing, and highlighted areas for development, such as the need to link cross-cutting priorities more closely with budget expenditure, and the need to reduce reporting burden.

Official website:

- Budget 2024 – Enhancing the Wellbeing of People Living in Ireland, www.gov.ie/pdf/?file=https://assets.gov.ie/274671/9c8a7ae3-43ea-467f-8fcf-bbcfe5dd0f4f.pdf#page=null
- **The Australian Capital Territory (ACT).** The Australian Capital Territory (ACT) has been the first jurisdiction in Australia to embed a Wellbeing Framework in its Budget process. The ACT Wellbeing Framework sets out the things that matter most to the quality of life of people, the environment, and institutions in the ACT. The framework includes 12 dimensions of wellbeing: Health; Safety; Living standards; Housing and home; Environment and climate; Social connections; Education and life-long learning; Time; Identity and belonging; Governance and institutions; Access and connectivity; and the Economy. The ACT [wellbeing framework](#) was officially released in March 2020, following a broad community engagement process that led to both the identification of the dimensions of wellbeing as well as the indicators that could measure these dimensions.

In 2021, the ACT government released its first wellbeing dashboard to help measure progress against these indicators. Subsequently, [Wellbeing Impact Assessments](#) (WIAs) were developed and implemented into budget business case protocols. A Wellbeing Impact Assessment (WIA) template helps the ACT Government plan for and make decisions based on a fuller understanding of the impacts of proposals on societal wellbeing, including both benefits and trade-offs.

Information sessions and training was provided to support public servants in analysing and considering wellbeing impacts as part of policy development and decision-making. The ACT government encourages government departments to use the WIAs at early stages of policy, programme and project development to think broad about wellbeing impacts and who within the community may be impacted. Following the implementation of the WIAs, the first [wellbeing-inspired ACT budget](#) was released in 2021.

Official website:

- <https://www.act.gov.au/wellbeing/wellbeing-framework>
- <https://www.treasury.act.gov.au/budget/budget-2023-24/budget-2023-24/wellbeing-budget>
- **Italy.** The 2016 reform of the Italian Budget Law stated that wellbeing indicators needed to be incorporated into budget planning, with the aim of creating a stronger link between government spending and societal wellbeing considerations. Starting from the 130 indicators in the *Rapporto sul Benessere equo e sostenibile* (Report on equitable and sustainable wellbeing, produced every year by ISTAT), a subset of twelve equitable and sustainable wellbeing (ESW) indicators were selected for integration into the budget cycle, spanning the domains of Health; Education and training; Economic wellbeing; Work-life balance; Safety; the Environment; and Quality of Services.

Since 2017, the Italian '[Economic and Financial Document](#)' includes an annual report on 12 indicators of equitable and sustainable wellbeing that is submitted to Parliament each year prior to the start of the budget discussions. The report shows the time trend for these 12 wellbeing indicators through retrospective analysis, with breakdowns by groups based on age, gender and region as well as forecasts for some indicators. Going forward, the Ministry aims to continue to increase the number of indicators for which forecasts are available and to refine the methodology for those already provided.

Official website:

- <https://www.istat.it/en/well-being-and-sustainability>

References

Jensen, K. & Thompson, C. (2020). Valuing Impacts. The contribution of CBAX to improved policy practices. *Policy Quarterly*, 16 (1), <https://doi.org/10.26686/pq.v16i1.6357>

OECD (2023), Economic Policy Making to Pursue Economic Welfare: OECD Report for the G7 Finance Ministers and Central Bank Governors, May 2023, Japan, OECD, Paris. https://www.oecd.org/economy/G7_Beyond_GDP_Economic_policy_making_to_pursue_economic_welfare_2023.pdf

Working Time Reduction

Reducing working hours presents a multifaceted solution to several contemporary challenges. It can help mitigate unemployment caused by technological advancements, promote environmental sustainability, and enhance individual wellbeing.

With the rapid pace of technological progress, many jobs traditionally performed by humans are now being automated. This shift necessitates a rethinking of employment structures and strategies to mitigate the adverse effects on the labour market. One effective strategy is the reduction of working hours. By decreasing the number of hours each individual works, businesses can distribute available work more evenly across a larger portion of the population. This not only provides employment opportunities to more people but also helps maintain economic stability by ensuring that more individuals have an income.

Moreover, the ability to produce more goods in a shorter amount of time has led to greater consumption of natural resources and higher levels of waste emissions. This trend poses a serious threat to environmental sustainability. Reducing working hours can play a role in addressing these environmental challenges. By aligning production with sustainable practices and moderating the pace of consumption, businesses can help reduce their ecological footprint.

Beyond economic and environmental considerations, reducing working hours has significant implications for individual wellbeing. A shorter workweek can improve work-life balance, providing people with more time for personal pursuits, family, and leisure activities. This can lead to increased job satisfaction, lower stress levels, and better overall health. In societies where long working hours are the norm, reducing work time can contribute to a cultural shift towards valuing personal time and wellbeing.

Case studies

In recent years, the push for shorter working hours without pay cuts — often referred to as a ‘four-day week’ — has gained significant momentum across Europe. The anticipated impact of automation and technological change on employment, coupled with a growing desire for more leisure time, has brought the reduction of working hours to the forefront of policy discussions. The impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on labour dynamics have also accelerated this trend, during which a rapid transition to remote work and unexpectedly increasing free time as workers abandoned their commutes or faced reduced working hours were seen in many sectors.

Given this rising interest in shorter working hours, evidence from existing trials of a 'four-day week' or similar schemes will become increasingly valuable for supportive workers, organizations, and politicians.

1 – Shorter workweek for the public sector in Iceland

- **Case description:**

From 2015 to 2019, Iceland conducted two large-scale trials of shorter working hours, reducing the standard 40-hour week to 35 or 36 hours without any pay cuts. These trials followed longstanding advocacy from grassroots organisations and unions. One trial was initiated in Reykjavík by the city authorities and the major trade union confederation BSRB, starting with a few dozen workers and eventually expanding to over 2,500 employees. The other trial, launched in 2017 between the Icelandic government and BSRB, included around 440 workers. Combined, these trials involved more than 1% of the country's working population.

The trial had two primary objectives: 1) to determine if reducing working hours could improve poor work-life balance, a key issue highlighted by the existing public campaign (BSRB, n.d.), and 2) to evaluate whether shorter working hours could boost productivity and to explore practical ways to achieve this. This was crucial, as the goal was to reduce working hours while keeping workers' salaries unchanged, requiring workplaces to maintain the same level of service provision as before the trial.

Two committees were established to manage the scheme, develop metrics to assess its success, and create strategies for reducing working hours. These reductions were tailored to the specific duties and operations of individual workplaces, although some predefined strategies were also applied. Many workplaces engaged in discussions on time management and efficiency. The trial began in March 2015 with two workplaces reducing their workers' hours, involving 66 staff members who transitioned from a 40-hour week to 35 or 36 hours, depending on the workplace. No changes were made in the control group workplace.

Over the following five years, the trial expanded nearly thirtyfold to include around 2,500 participants, driven by early positive results. It eventually encompassed a diverse range of workplaces, including offices, preschools, city maintenance facilities, care homes for individuals with disabilities and special needs, and even the Reykjavík City Mayor's office. The trial's objectives also broadened. First, to determine if the working hours of those on

irregular shift patterns could be successfully reduced. Second, to assess if the long-term effects of shorter hours would mirror the positive short-term outcomes observed.

- **Policy impact:**

Throughout the trials, extensive data was gathered on various metrics such as wellbeing, performance, and work-life balance. Overall, the results indicate that the reductions in working hours achieved the following: 1) maintained or enhanced productivity and service delivery; and 2) improved workers' wellbeing and work-life balance.

Moreover, concerns about overwork were effectively addressed through thoughtful trial design. According to the Icelandic trials, "the stated reduction in working hours did lead to staff actually working less as a direct result of workplaces implementing new work strategies, and through organising tasks via cooperation between workers and managers."

These trials demonstrated that reducing working hours can profoundly enhance work-life balance. Given Iceland's initial challenges in this area, the positive outcomes reported by participants strongly advocate for shorter working hours as a key strategy for other governments aiming to improve work-life balance and wellbeing in their economies. These benefits include:

- Reduced stress at home, with more time available for partners and domestic activities.
- Increased time spent with extended family and friends.
- More personal time for hobbies, interests, or simply rest.
- Greater flexibility for household chores during the workweek, enhancing weekend quality.
- Improved distribution of domestic responsibilities among men in heterosexual partnerships.
- Positive effects for single parents, often facing significant time constraints.
- Beneficial impacts on extended family and friends, who enjoyed increased contact with trial participants, even if they themselves did not directly reduce their working hours.

Meanwhile, control workplaces working a full working week showed no such improvements.

The scale of the trials, along with the variety of workplaces involved and the abundance of both quantitative and qualitative data, offers groundbreaking evidence supporting the effectiveness of reducing working hours. Following the success of the trials, Icelandic trade unions and their confederations secured permanent reductions in working hours for tens of thousands of their members nationwide. As a result, approximately 86% of Iceland's entire workforce has now either transitioned to shorter working hours or gained the right to do so.

- **Link to external source:**
 - <https://www.bsrb.is/en/skodun/the-policy-onregardingpolicies/a-shorter-work-week>
 - https://en.aldais/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/ICELAND_4DW.pdf

2 – UK's four-day week Pilot

In June to December 2022, the UK conducted the largest trial of a four-day workweek to date, involving 61 companies and approximately 2,900 workers. In early 2022, the 4 Day Week Campaign, 4 Day Week Global, and Autonomy launched a recruitment drive for companies and non-profit organisations to join a six-month trial.

The trial was designed with a two-month preparation phase for participants, offering workshops, coaching, mentoring, and peer support. This initiative drew upon the experiences of companies that had already transitioned to shorter working weeks, as well as insights from leading research and consultancy organisations.

Participating companies, spanning various sectors and sizes, were given flexibility in implementing different types of working time reductions or four-day work week models, as long as salaries remained unchanged and employees experienced a 'meaningful' reduction in work hours.

Rejecting the notion of a one-size-fits-all approach to the four-day work week, each company crafted policies tailored to its specific industry, organisational challenges, departmental structures, and work cultures. This approach led to the development of a variety of four-day week models, including traditional 'Friday off' arrangements, as well as 'staggered', 'decentralised', 'annualised', and 'conditional' structures.

- **Policy impact:**

Administrative data from companies, survey data from employees, alongside a range of interviews conducted over the pilot period, providing measurement points that were collected at the beginning, middle and end of the trial. Significant benefits of shorter working hours were evident in employees' well-being. Comparative data show that by the end of the trial, 39% of employees experienced reduced stress, and 71% reported lower levels of burnout. Moreover, levels of anxiety, fatigue, and sleep issues decreased, contributing to improvements in both mental and physical health. Throughout the trial period, measures of work-life balance also saw improvement. Employees found it easier to balance work with family and social commitments, with 54% noting improved balance between work and household responsibilities. Additionally, employees reported higher satisfaction with household finances, relationships, and time management. Furthermore, 60% of employees noted an increased ability to juggle paid work with caregiving responsibilities, and 62% found it easier to integrate work with their social lives.

The data indicate that the trial was successful. Out of the 61 participating companies, 56 have chosen to continue with the four-day week (92%), and 18 have confirmed that the policy is now permanent.

Additional key business metrics also demonstrated positive impacts from shorter working hours. For instance, companies generally maintained their revenue during the trial period, with an average increase of 1.4% weighted by company size across participating organisations. Compared to similar periods in previous years, organisations reported an average revenue increase of 35%, indicating robust growth despite reduced working hours. Moreover, the turnover rate among employees at participating companies notably decreased, dropping by 57% throughout the trial period. For many, the benefits of a four-day week outweighed monetary considerations. A notable 15% of employees expressed that they would not trade their newly adopted four-day schedule for any amount of money to return to a five-day workweek.

- **Link to external source:**

- <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/60b956cbe7bf6f2efd86b04e/t/63f3df56276b3e6d7870207e/1676926845047/UK-4-Day-Week-Pilot-Results-Report-2023.pdf>

3 – Jornada de 4 días in Valencia, Spain

- **Case description:**

The City Council of Valencia launched a pilot initiative regarding the implementation of a 4-day workweek across the entire city for 4 consecutive weeks in April/May. They took advantage of two Mondays in April and the first Monday in May being holidays, thus declaring an additional Monday as a holiday. This ensured that for these 4 consecutive weeks, the workweek consisted of only 4 days. Specifically, the pilot took place from April 10th to May 7th, 2023. This experience has allowed to observe how citizens' behaviours and habits change and what the medium-term impacts are on the environment, health, and personal well-being, and to a lesser extent (due to the short duration of this experience and the lack of intervention on productivity factors), on certain economic sectors. This measure has affected all workers employed in the city. This includes approximately 360,000 people, of whom 176,000 are women and 184,000 are men, primarily working in the service sector.

The objectives set forth by this pilot program were: 1) Generate knowledge and scientific evidence regarding the impacts on health, wellbeing, and climate that may result from reducing the workweek. 2) Contribute to improving the wellbeing and health of the population. 3) Contribute to the fight against climate change.

- **Policy impact:**

In order to verify the potential effects of this measure on those who have worked four days a week for a month, quantitative sources of information have been utilised, complemented by interviews with experts in various fields. The primary data sources include a survey conducted on a significant sample of the population (2,100 people) and all the information gathered through sensors deployed throughout the city by the Smart City Office of the Valencia City Council, which provides insights into air quality, traffic, and other factors. The results reported – among others – an increase of 37,7% in time allocated for physical activity, 46,1% for reading and 35,5% in home-made food consumption. 35% of participants reported lower stress levels, 64% slept more and, in general reported a better health status. Finally, the population has highly valued this measure (with an average of 7 points on a scale of 0 to 10), considering, to a large extent, that it has health benefits, improves work-life balance, enriches social life, and contributes to generating a positive impact on certain workplace environment issues.

After analysing all the gathered information, it was concluded that the reduction of working hours has improved the health and wellbeing of the workers. The data shows an improvement in self-perceived health status, a significant reduction in stress levels, and better feelings regarding fatigue, happiness, mood, and personal satisfaction. Work-life balance and personal/family life harmony have also improved. It is also noteworthy that

those who consume tobacco and alcohol have done so to a greater extent during these weeks. Visiting parks, gardens, and natural spaces is another activity where survey respondents report spending more time than usual.

In environmental terms, a 4-day workweek has the potential to contribute to traffic calming and air quality. Regarding the effects of this measure across sectors, the findings indicate that there may have been an overload in emergency medical services. The commercial sector, on the other hand, reports a decrease in sales due to a shift in public spending towards the leisure sector. In fact, it is noted that hospitality and tourism have served a greater number of customers.

- **Link to external source:**

- https://www.lasnaves.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Informe_4Dies_Digital-4.pdf

References

- <https://skemman.is/handle/1946/29608>
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376397430_Workplace-level_interventions_and_trials_of_working_time_reduction_A_scoping_review
- <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/60b956cbe7bf6f2efd86b04e/t/6387be703530a824fc3adf58/1669840498593/The+Four+Day+Week-+Assessing+Global+Trials+of+Reduced+Work+Time+with+No+Reduction+in+Pay+%E2%80%93+F+%E2%80%93+30112022.pdf>
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269702758_THE_EXPERIMENTS_OF_REDUCED_WORKING_HOURS_IN_FINLAND

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